

Maternity Care Services for Women with Disabilities during Pregnancy and Childbirth in Switzerland

Learning from the experiences of women with spinal cord injuries and
their practitioners to optimise maternity care services

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I remember my accident and acquiring a spinal cord injury (SCI) in 1999, which has largely shaped my personal life and my professional career. Reflecting on this formative period of my life, this and several factors were responsible for my subsequent strong interest in the theme of this thesis.

First, the subjects of health and health care provision are linked to so many aspects of human life—our preoccupation with these themes truly starts at birth and ends with death. Questions, concerns, reflections or decisions about health and health care are continuously present in our daily lives and may gain even greater importance after the experience of an accident or even something more gratifying, such as giving birth to a child. It is no wonder that research on health services has always seemed to be a very concrete field, based on reality and the useful applications of theoretical scientific concepts as they relate to the experiences of affected persons.

Second, my first profession as a Marketing and Communication Specialist revealed my interest for the gaps existing in women's health that I myself also experienced. Together with other women in wheelchairs, I built a community for women like us. For 10 years, I learned the needs of this community and trained myself in Germany in the field of reproductive health communication. One project of the community was the creation of an educational book that displays a photo series of pregnancy and birth with an SCI.

Third, the application of health care services research to the maternity care sector and those with disabilities was still a new and rather surprising undertaking for the SCI research community, as the field is dominated by traditional medical health professionals. Some medical health professionals noticed early on that a holistic approach to exploring the barriers and opportunities to accessing maternal health care services could be beneficial for women affected by SCI. In particular, Professor Jürgen Pannek of the Swiss Paraplegic Center encouraged and supported my investigation in this field.

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GENERAL INTRODUCTION

INTRODUCTION

MATERNITY AND MATERNITY CARE IN EUROPE AND SWITZERLAND

Every year, approximately 4.7 million European women experience childbirth [1]. Optimal maternal and child health are fundamental for societal well-being. Maternal health involves the health care dimensions of family planning, preconception, prenatal and postnatal care to ensure a safe and enjoyable experience giving birth [2]. Reports from the European Childbirth Cultures, Concerns, and Consequences (COST) Research Program (Action IS0907, 2011–2014) not only show that maternal health has improved in Europe over the last two decades, but also address new concerns about preventable harms caused by either medical treatment or advice [1]. Preventable harms can stem from the side effects of possible drug interactions, complications from a procedure or treatment, medical errors, negligence or anxiety in the physician or treatment provider.

Maternity care is a universal human right for every pregnant woman in every health system. Therefore, maternity care must be sufficiently comprehensive and flexible to respond to the medical and social needs of women and their families [3, 4]. How is the Swiss health system prepared for these challenges?

Overall, Switzerland offers high-quality maternity care [5, 6]. Services are sufficiently accessible and available to the general population, though the density of gynaecologists is lower in rural areas than in urban spaces [7]. Regarding the availability and accessibility of care institutions, pregnant women have a variety of choices for both prenatal care and, later, childbirth. For antenatal care, pregnant women can use a midwife, who will visit the expectant mother's home or attend to her at the midwife's practice, birth house or hospital. Women can also visit an obstetrician or general practitioner (GP) in a private practice or a hospital. Finally, some women combine the services of a midwife and a doctor. In Switzerland, only 6% of the women choose to give birth in a birth house or at home [8]. Others choose a medical facility, generally a hospital. Although, for most women, pregnancy and childbirth are treasured and positive experiences [9], health services must be able to respond appropriately to those individuals who may require highly specialised care for existing health problems, including women with disabilities.

In Europe, nearly 41 million women aged 15 and over report having a disability [10]. Disability is an evolving concept and part of the human condition. Many people become either temporarily or permanently impaired at some point in their lives. Health and disability are measured using the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF), a classification tool endorsed by the World Health Organization (WHO) in 2001 [11]. The ICF defines 'disability' as an umbrella term for impairments, activity limitations and participation restrictions. The term refers to the negative aspects of the interaction between an individual (with a health condition) and the individual's contextual (environmental and personal) factors [12]. Following the ICF definition, the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD), created in 2006, acknowledges that disability is 'an evolving concept' and points out that 'disability results from the interaction between persons with impairments and attitudinal and environmental barriers that hinder their full and effective participation in society on an equal basis with others' [13]. Defining disability as an interaction means that a disability is not a personal attribute. Furthermore, it suggests that barriers can be addressed to improve the day-to-day social participation of people with disabilities [14]. In particular, because of advances in medicine, rehabilitation, community participation and disability destigmatisation, an increasing number of women with disabilities choose to become mothers [11–13].

HEALTH CARE WITH DISABILITIES: MATERNITY CARE

'Health care' are services provided to individuals or communities by health practitioners and the purpose is the maintenance or improvement of health [15]. Access to health care varies across countries, groups and individuals, influenced by social and economic conditions and health policies [16, 17]. Barriers in access to health care providers and facilities have been reported from many women with physical disabilities, who must confront environmental, structural and attitudinal barriers while accessing health care [18, 19]. The environmental barriers include public and private transportation, health practices and equipment accessibility. People with disabilities perceive public transportation as being insufficiently accessible and disabled parking options as unavailable or inadequate. Health practitioners' practices, examination rooms and diagnostic equipment are often not accessible to or adequate for people with disabilities [18, 20, 21]. Structural barriers can include a lack of health care plans adapted to consumers, limited provider choice and referrals. Inadequate health care plans can hinder the reception of services, compromising quality due to time constraints and due to staff shortness. Finally, attitudinal barriers can include a lack of provider knowledge about disabilities [22,

23] and negative attitudes and/or inattention to patients [24-26]. The lack of provider knowledge about disabilities can cover such issues as how to treat disability-related health problems and understanding disability- and non-disability-related health problems [19, 27].

Health practitioners have similar perceptions. With respect to providing health care for disabled people, health practitioners have been remarkably consistent in identifying several barriers, including care limitations, physical access and transportation restrictions, limitations in professionals' knowledge and attitudes, communication gaps and health system failures [28-30]. They have stated unequivocally that disabled patients take more time and are more complex regarding the provision of care [30]. Several health practitioners acknowledge that their facilities lack wheelchair access and/or equipment appropriate to accommodate people with a disability [30, 31]. Health practitioners also admit that they are unaware of the correct way to provide physical assistance to disabled patients and, in some cases, that they are unwilling to help them [30]. The literature shows that disabled patients may be systematically excluded from family practices because of the burden they are perceived to impose on physicians' time [29, 32, 33]. It has been suggested that education programmes for young doctors should educate them in coordinating care, accessing resources and communicating about disability issues [30].

While many studies have examined health care access for women with disabilities in general, there is very little evidence about disabled women's access to maternal health services. Two US studies reported the same barriers described above being valid for maternity care and noted that pregnant women with disabilities require longer examinations [21, 34]. A UK study [35] reported that women with disabilities were likely to have more antenatal checks and ultrasound scans, to be delivered by caesarean section and to have longer hospital stays. Disabled women also had fewer choices concerning place of birth and were less involved in decisions about their labour and birth care. A Norwegian study about women with physical disabilities reported inadequate perinatal care due to negative attitudes and limited knowledge and experience among health care professionals. Furthermore, expecting mothers with disabilities often reported negative experiences with some aspects of care, such as communication and involvement in decisions, particularly in relation to birth procedures [35, 36].

In summary, women with disabilities seem to experience important disadvantages in attempting to access health care services, in particular maternity services. Thus, it is critical to ask: What maternity services are the health system offering, and how do

physicians' perceptions of disabled women and behaviours towards them affect these women's access to maternity care?

Previous research points to a potential gap in maternal health services with respect to responding to the health needs of pregnant women, even across highly developed countries [1]. There is a need to better understand the interactions between pregnancy and maternity services in women with disabilities to optimise available services [37, 38]. Focusing on the accessibility and availability of maternity services is a primary concern because it lays the groundwork for care reception. Persons with disabilities can only be adequately supported if we have a full understanding of how the health system is currently meeting their needs.

Against this background, Switzerland offers an interesting context for study, as it is a resource-rich country with a high-quality health system and an increasing interest in ensuring health access for disabled people. Switzerland ratified the Disability Convention on May 15th, 2014 [39].

To study the maternity care services situation of women with disabilities, spinal cord injury (SCI) may serve as a case in point. An 'SCI' is major health condition that affects all body functions below the lesion level, and they may have a substantial impact on health needs and health services use, particularly against the background of environmental barriers, such as inaccessible infrastructure and negative attitudes [34, 40].

Women with SCI are less likely than able-bodied women to become mothers. Within Switzerland, an estimated 53% of women between 35 and 64 years have children [41]; however, there are no records about motherhood with SCI. Studies from the US and England report that 14 to 18% of women with an SCI have children after their injury [42-44].

LIVING WITH AN SCI: CHALLENGES FOR MATERNITY AND MATERNITY CARE

An SCI is caused by a lesion of the central nervous system inside the spinal column [45]. Changes to the cord's normal motor, sensory or autonomic function can be either temporary or permanent [46]. The severity of the impairment depends on the neurological level and the completeness of the lesion [47] Figure 1.

Injuries to the cervical spine (C1-C8) result in impairment to the arms, lower body and legs (i.e. tetraplegia) [48]. A thoracic or lumbar lesion (T1-L5) affects the legs and,

depending on the lesion level, also the muscles of the trunk (i.e. paraplegia) [49]. In Switzerland, of those who suffer an SCI, 69% become paraplegic, and 31% become tetraplegic [50]. Depending on where the spinal cord and nerve roots are damaged, symptoms can vary widely and affect body structures and functions of the digestive and genitourinary system [51, 52]. Besides having important implications for the body, an SCI has severe implications for participation in daily life and for quality of life [53, 54]. Persons with an SCI have more difficulty performing everyday activities, reintegrating into work life and being active members of society [55].

During clinical rehabilitation, persons with SCI learn to deal with the physical consequences and secondary complications of their SCI and are prepared to function as independently as possible in everyday life [56, 57]. To live a fulfilled life, it is important for persons with SCI to enjoy satisfying and rewarding sexual lives, have fulfilling intimate relationships and/or have families [58, 59]. An SCI does not impair fertility in either men or women. Male partners with an SCI frequently require urological assistance to achieve pregnancy [60]. However, regardless of their level of injury or severity, women with an SCI may become pregnant naturally following a phase of amenorrhea [61, 62].

Women with SCIs are prone to high-risk pregnancies due to possible secondary complications that can arise during pre-term labour and birth [63]. The available evidence suggests that worsened spasticity, high blood pressure, respiratory problems, worsened bladder management and swelling or water deposits in the legs are reported more often during pregnancies in women with SCIs [42, 47, 64]. It is impossible to predict when or if secondary conditions will develop during pregnancy. For example, headaches and nausea are common during pregnancy, but a pounding headache and nausea in a woman with an SCI may also signify suddenly high blood pressure, also called autonomic dysreflexia (AD) [47, 65, 66]. Women with SCIs commonly experience urinary tract infections (UTIs) [67], and they are at even higher risk during pregnancy. This can lead to a kidney infection (pyelonephritis) [68]. Medication for spasticity, bladder and bowel management, pain or depression may have to be adapted or stopped during pregnancy [68-70]. Several of the secondary complications of an SCI can cause obstetrical challenges (e.g. UTIs can trigger early labour) [62, 71]. Birth may be difficult for women with injuries at T10 and above because of their inability to feel uterine contractions. Birth may be indicated by increased spasticity or, for women with lesions at T6 and above, by AD [70]. Most cases require pre-term delivery [70]. The possible health risks and secondary complications can result in a high utilisation of health care. The combination of physiological changes related to pregnancy and SCIs can temporarily or permanently affect the health and function of women with SCIs who become pregnant [68].

SCI influence on pregnancy

Functions affected (nerves)

Breathing (C1-4, head and neck movement (C2), heart rate (C4-6)

CERVICAL DIVISION C1-7

Shoulder, elbow and wrist movement (C5-7)
Hand and finger movement (C7-T1)

THORACIC DIVISION T1-12

Sympathetic tone (T1-12) (including temperature regulation) and trunk stability (T2-12)

LUMBAR DIVISION L1-5

Hip motion (L2) and knee extension (L3)

SACRAL DIVISION S1-5

Coccyx

Lesion above T4: A ventilation assessment in pregnancy is advised.

Lesion above T6: Autonomic dysreflexia may occur in women with an injury at or above the T10 level, especially above T6.

Lesion above T10: Unable to feel uterine contractions and labour pains.

Lesion above T12: Increased risk of malpresentation at term.

FIGURE 1: Diagram showing functions affected and features of SCI at various vertebrae in relation to pregnancy

DOCTORAL THESIS

This doctoral thesis focuses on the maternity care situation of Swiss women with SCI during pregnancy and childbirth and starts from the assumption that current maternity care services are not well prepared to meet their health needs. Based on this assumption, learning from the experiences of women with SCI and their practitioners is one potential way to optimise maternal care services.

First, as an initial step towards understanding service needs, it is advantageous to have access to high-quality data about health complications which is of particular interest for pregnancy counselling and to help guide the care and anticipation of potential complications in complex pregnancies. Unfortunately, no high-quality data exists [72, 73].

Second, it is necessary to understand the issues related not only to acute health problems, but also service utilisation and related outcomes in women with SCI [74, 75]. Thus, the research focus must be transferred from clinical factors to a more complex and holistic view. One approach to systematically investigate maternal care utilisation is to employ a health services research approach investigating the contexts under which health care services are provided [76].

Third, pregnancy with an SCI needs special care and can have multiple complications, and its management does not rest exclusively in the obstetrics field. Previous research reveals that health practitioners lack information and specific knowledge, and they fail to consistently and adequately respond to the needs of pregnant women with SCIs [77-79]. Although the medical complexity reflects the interactions between pregnant women with SCIs and the larger health care system, there is a paucity of research involving health practitioners' views and experiences in delivering care [26, 80].

The population-based community survey of the Swiss Spinal Cord Injury Cohort Study (SwiSCI) [81], the largest community survey on persons with SCIs in Europe, offers an opportunity to access the community of women with SCIs.

OVERALL OBJECTIVE AND SPECIFIC AIMS

The overall objective of this doctoral thesis is to examine the maternity care situation of Swiss women with SCIs during pregnancy and childbirth from the perspective of the affected women and their practitioners to optimise maternity care services in Switzerland. The thesis comprises three studies, which seek to address the gaps described in the introduction and accomplish the overall objective by achieving the following specific aims:

- i. to identify the medical complications of women with SCIs during pregnancy and childbirth in Switzerland and to describe how they deal with these complications;
- ii. to identify the perceived service needs of women with SCIs during pregnancy and childbirth in Switzerland and to reconstruct their experiences of health care service utilisation based on their accounts; and
- iii. to reconstruct the perceptions and experiences of health care providers caring for women with SCIs during pregnancy and childbirth in Switzerland.

OUTLINE OF THE THESIS

The first study, described in **Chapter 2**, explores the frequency of medical complications in pregnant Swiss women with SCIs. The aim of this study is to build a deeper understanding of medical needs for health services by using quantitative indicators. The second study interviewing mothers with SCIs, in **Chapter 3**, investigates the pregnancy and birth care experiences of Swiss mothers with SCIs in relation to health services use. The aim of this study is to identify the perceived health needs, the services provided and used, and the results. The last study with practitioners, in **Chapter 4**, investigates the experiences of health practitioners in delivering care to women with SCIs during pregnancy and childbirth. The purpose of this study is to find out how health practitioners with expertise in one specialty (e.g. gynaecology, urology, spinal cord medicine etc.) experience providing care to pregnant women with SCIs. In **Chapter 5**, the main findings and conclusions of the thesis are summarised and discussed alongside potential implications and suggestions for future research. Finally, the **Appendix** presents the medical and demographic questionnaire and the semi-structured interview guides used in this thesis. The aim of this notes are to provide background information on the data collection and to report on its accuracy and its reproducibility.

PREGNANCY-RELATED COMPLICATIONS
IN WOMEN WITH SPINAL CORD INJURY

Medical complications during pregnancy and childbirth in women with SCI in Switzerland

Bertschy S, Bostan C, Meyer T, Pannek J, Spinal Cord, 2016, 54(3):183-187.

ABSTRACT

Study design: A retrospective interview study of mothers with spinal cord injuries (SCIs) who gave birth over the last 15 years.

Objectives: To identify the medical complications of women with SCIs during pregnancy and childbirth in Switzerland and to describe how they dealt with these complications.

Settings: Swiss Paraplegic Research in Nottwil, the University of Lausanne, and participants' homes.

Methods: Data were collected by self-reported questionnaires and descriptive analysis was conducted.

Results: Seventeen women with SCIs who gave birth to 23 children were included. Thirteen of the women were paraplegics and four were tetraplegics. All of them practiced an independent bladder management. Three women changed their bladder management techniques during pregnancy. Five women reported an increased bladder evacuation frequency during pregnancy, and six women reported a new onset or increase in incontinence. We observed no significant increase in bowel dysfunction or skin breakdown due to their pregnancies. Ten women were hospitalised during the course of their pregnancies. Aside from urinary tract infections (UTIs)/pyelonephritis, women were hospitalised for falls, hypertension, pneumonia, preeclampsia, pre-term labour, or tachycardia.

Conclusion: The results of our study clearly demonstrated that although medical complications are not infrequent during pregnancy in women with SCIs, pregnancy and delivery in this group of women is possible without posing intolerable risks to the mothers or the children. Urologic problems seemed to be the most frequent complication during pregnancy.

INTRODUCTION

A traumatic spinal cord injury (SCI) does not impair fertility in women. Following a phase of amenorrhea, women with SCIs may become pregnant [61]. As researchers, we assert an increasing interest in this topic of women with SCIs.

Pregnancy, childbirth, parenting, and motherhood in women with SCIs have all been researched from medical [37, 66, 69, 82, 83] and psycho-social [36, 75, 82, 83] perspectives. In addition, health care providers' knowledge [22] and accessibility as well as the availability of services [21, 27, 84, 85] have been assessed. However, different topics related to pregnancy and SCI care are still under-researched and therefore require more focused research. One of these topics is the potential medical complications that occur during pregnancy as addressed from the perspectives of the pregnant women.

Urologic complications are of particular importance in pregnant women with SCIs. First, virtually all patients with SCIs suffer from neurogenic lower urinary tract dysfunction (NLUTD) [86]. An elevated storage pressure, either due to low bladder compliance or neurogenic detrusor overactivity, is a major risk factor for renal deterioration [87]. Therefore, the primary objective of bladder management is to prevent renal damage. Furthermore, NLUTD may also lead to incontinence and recurrent symptomatic urinary tract infections (UTIs). In patients with SCIs, UTIs are the leading cause of septicemia and are associated with a significantly increased mortality rate [88]. In addition, both UTIs and incontinence significantly impair the quality of life of affected persons [89].

Pregnancy is also known to have an impact on the lower urinary tract of neurologically intact women. The risk for bacteriuria for example is elevated in pregnant women [90]. Thus, pregnant women with SCIs are likely at a higher risk for urologic complications.

As a consequence, pregnant women with SCIs require specific spinal cord medicine and urological care. However, empirical evidence on urologic complications in pregnant women with SCIs is scarce. A recent review demonstrated that there are virtually no data about the incidence, severity, and management of urologic complications in these patients [68]. To get a clearer picture, we collected data from women who were concerned about their urologic health and other specific SCI medical problems during their pregnancies. The objective of this study was to identify any medical complications and to describe how women with SCIs dealt with those complications during pregnancy and childbirth in Switzerland.

STUDY DESIGN

A descriptive study was conducted that included mothers with traumatic or non-traumatic SCIs between 18 and 54 years of age with permanent residence in Switzerland who had given birth within the past 15 years and after their SCIs.

The study participants were recruited for a qualitative study. The aim of this qualitative study was to examine the health service experiences of women with SCIs during pregnancy and childbirth [91]. The recruitment process was previously described [91]. In brief, women were recruited through the Swiss Spinal Cord Injury Cohort [81] database and through snowball sampling in the disability community [92]. Both lists were matched and all retrieved names (94 names in total) were cross-checked. A total of 34 individuals were excluded based on language and age (54 years of age and older); in addition, 7 names were doubles. A total of 60 women were invited to participate in the study. The response rate was 70 % (42 women). These respondents were contacted by telephone for a second eligibility check. Of these mothers, 18 did not meet the eligibility criteria and seven declined to participate. Seventeen mothers expressed interest in taking part in the study, representing a final response rate of 28%. This sample might not be considered a representative sample of pregnant women with SCIs in Switzerland since there is no data on the total number of pregnant women and their distribution.

DATA COLLECTION

After the qualitative interview sessions, participating women were asked to fill out a questionnaire and to retrospectively report on the most frequent secondary medical problems that resulted from their SCIs and that had developed during their pregnancies (Appendix 1). The list was developed by considering the current literature and by involving health providers who had cared for pregnant women with SCIs [93]. The questionnaire specifically asked about skin problems, bowel function, UTI frequency, mode of delivery, decubital ulcers, hospital admissions, alterations in medication, respiratory tract problems, and changes in NLUTD symptoms.

In addition, patients were asked whether they took prophylactic measures against UTIs, decubitus, and deep vein thrombosis (DVT) as well as what those measures were. Since we were also interested in information related to women's bladder voiding techniques, we collected data from qualitative interviews. A recent study

showed that voiding technique has a major influence on the incidence rates of UTIs [94].

DATA ANALYSIS

Descriptive statistics were used to analyse the data.

RESULTS

DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

The demographic characteristics of the 17 participants are presented in Table 1. Thirteen women were paraplegic and four were tetraplegic. While the mean age was 21 at the time of the injury, the mean age at the time of giving birth was 33. The 17 women gave birth to 23 children altogether after their SCIs, and two women each had one child before their SCIs. The mean interval between SCI incidences and the birth of a first child was 12 years. At the time of motherhood, all mothers were either married or had stable relationships, and all women had health insurance.

TABLE 1 DEMOGRAPHICS OF PARTICIPANTS

	<i>Mean (range)</i>
Age, years	
at time of injury	21 [2-37]
at time of motherhood	33 [25-40]
Time SCI-motherhood	12 [2-23]
Education	n
Apprenticeship	5
Bachelor degree	4
Master degree	6
Postgraduate degree	2
Type of injury	n
Complete paraplegia	7
Incomplete paraplegia	6
Complete tetraplegia	1
Incomplete tetraplegia	3

Pregnancy-related complications in women with SCI

TABLE 2 HEALTH COMPLICATIONS DURING PREGNANCY IN WOMAN WITH SCI, TREATMENTS AND PREVENTION MEASURES

<i>Type of complication</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Treatment</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Prevention measure *</i>	<i>N</i>
Skin (pressure sores)	0			Increased rest	2
Thrombosis	0			Leg elevation	5
				Medication (anticoagulants)	2
				Compressive stockings	9
				Taking shower	4
				Lymph drainage	1
Urinary tract infections	11	Antibiotics	8		
		Cranberries	1		
		Homeopathy	1		
Respiration problems	1				
Bowel problems	10			Laxative tea	1

*Multiple answers

Specific changes in health management and medical complications during pregnancy due to SCIs

Table 2 shows the health complications during pregnancy in women with SCIs, their treatments, and the prevention measures taken.

No women reported skin problems. Two women paid special attention to the prevention of decubital ulcers (by resting more). Ten women performed prophylactic measures against DVT where nine of them used compressive stockings. No incidences of DVT were diagnosed during pregnancy.

Table 3 shows the bladder/bowel dysfunctions and medication changes that occurred in women with SCIs during pregnancy. Constipation was the most frequently reported complaint concerning bowel dysfunction, whereas diarrhoea, flatulence, and abdominal gas occurred rarely. In summary, pregnancy did not significantly increase bowel dysfunction. Concerning drug treatments, three women either stopped taking their pain medications (such as Citalopram or Tegretol) or their anticholinergic treatment for detrusor overactivity. Two women reported that they stopped taking all their medication.

Pregnancy-related complications in women with SCI

TABLE 3 BLADDER/BOWEL DYSFUNCTION AND MEDICATION CHANGES DURING PREGNANCY IN WOMAN WITH SCI

<i>Dysfunction</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>How/What</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Treatment</i>	<i>N</i>
Bladder dysfunction	13	Frequency of bladder evacuation	6*	Change in therapy	4
		Incontinence	9*		
Bowel dysfunction	10	Improved function	1		
		Diarrhoea	1		
		Flatulence	1		
		Constipation	7		
Medication	8	Thrombosis prophylaxis	1		
		Iron supplementation	4		
		Folic acid	2		
		Vitamin supplementation	1		
		Antihypertensive medication	1		
		Don't remember	3		

* Multiple answers

TABLE 4 DELIVERY, BIRTH TYPE AND ANAESTHESIA INDICATIONS FOR 16 OUT OF 17 WOMAN*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>N</i>	
Week of delivery before the term (weeks)** mean [min, max]	2.4 [1, 5]	
Type of birth	Caesarean section	11
	Vaginal birth	5
Anaesthesia	General anaesthesia	4
	Epidural anaesthesia	8

* One woman was still pregnant at the time of data collection

** Pre-term N = 14

Regarding bladder management, ten women reported the use of intermittent self-catheterisation, four had an anterior root ("Brindley") stimulator, and three emptied their bladder using the Credé method.

Three women changed their *bladder management techniques* during pregnancy. One used an indwelling catheter prescribed by her gynaecologist, one reduced her

anticholinergic treatment for detrusor overactivity, and one did not perform onabotulinumtoxin injections in the detrusor at the scheduled times.

Five women reported an increased *bladder evacuation frequency* during pregnancy; six women reported the onset of incontinence or an increase in incontinence. As a consequence, one woman took the initiative to use larger incontinence devices (diapers). While nine women experienced no change in UTI frequency, six women reported an increased number of UTIs. None of the women using a stimulator reported an increase in UTI frequency during pregnancy. Although UTIs were most frequently treated by antibiotics (n=7), four women did use some combination of homeopathy, UTI prophylaxis, and phytotherapy (bearberry-leaf tea and cranberry extract) Table 3.

Ten women were hospitalised during the course of their pregnancies. In four women, UTIs/pyelonephritis led to hospitalisation, making it the most common reason for hospitalisation during pregnancy. Besides UTI/pyelonephritis, women were hospitalised for falls, hypertension, pneumonia, preeclampsia, pre-term labour, or tachycardia.

OBSTETRICAL ISSUES

One woman was interviewed during (the last trimenon of) pregnancy, and sixteen of the seventeen women gave birth to at least one child. In 15 women, delivery took place before the calculated date of birth (from one to five weeks early). Five women had vaginal births, whereas eleven women underwent caesarean sections Table 4. Moreover, whereas all women received either general (8 women) or epidural (3 women) anaesthesia for their caesarean sections, only one woman who gave vaginal birth required general anaesthesia. This woman also delivered her child on the scheduled day.

DISCUSSION

We described the medical complications that occurred during the course of pregnancy in women with SCIs as retrospectively reported by the women. In particular, we assessed skin, bladder, bowel, and respiratory problems as well as the prophylactic and treatment measures used by the pregnant women. In addition, we identified the women's experiences of any medical problems related to their deliveries.

According to women's reports, the majority of changes in medical procedures were related to bladder management, including changes in medication and changes in bladder evacuation methods. These changes led to an increased rate of UTIs in a substantial subset of women. It is well-known that the use of indwelling catheters leads to an increased UTI rate [95]. Most anticholinergic drugs should not be taken at least during the first trimester of pregnancy because foetal malformations were observed in animal experiments that used these drugs [96], and onabotulinum toxin is also not licensed for use during pregnancy. Given this, ineffective treatment of detrusor overactivity may occur, such as by decreasing the dosage of anticholinergic medication or by suspending onabotulinumtoxin injections in the detrusor. This usually leads to incontinence, which is frequently treated by inserting an indwelling catheter, especially if intermittent catheterisation becomes more difficult during the course of pregnancy. In addition, detrusor overactivity per se is linked to an increase in UTI frequency [97]. Therefore, the need to alter treatments for detrusor overactivity during pregnancy may increase the risk of having UTIs. Patients with Brindley stimulators neither performed intermittent catheterisation nor received treatment for detrusor overactivity. Given that the detrusor becomes areflexive after this procedure [98], it was not surprising that this group of women did not suffer from UTIs during pregnancy.

In four women, hospitalization was required due to pyelonephritis. It is well known that pyelonephritis may lead to premature labour. As the overwhelming majority of the study participants (14/16) experienced premature labour in our study, we cannot reliably relate pyelonephritis to this phenomenon in our study.

The study results show that women used numerous prophylactic measures during pregnancy to avoid complications. No skin breakdown or thrombosis occurred during pregnancy. One possible reason for this enhanced bodily awareness could be the educational nature of the rehabilitation programs in the rehabilitation centres in Switzerland.

Given the high number of bowel problems in persons with SCIs [99], we were surprised that none of the women asked their physicians for medical advice concerning these problems. We assume that this complication was not sufficiently important to the women to warrant seeking help. Additionally, we think that these women may believe that pregnancy requires such forms of tolerance.

Several studies [64, 100, 101] describe higher rates (ranging from 18% to 49%) of caesarean sections among women with SCIs compared to able-bodied women, and it is unclear whether the predominant causes are gynaecologic in origin [64, 100]. In an American study [101], the most common reasons for a caesarean section are "elective

repeat procedure, failure in progress in labour, and pelvic instability.” In 2013 in Switzerland, every third birth occurred through a caesarean section [102], which is an average frequency compared to other European countries. Our results also show a high tendency toward caesarean sections (69%) in women with SCIs. The reasons for this finding are unclear. A qualitative study examined the subjective health needs and services used by women with SCIs from Switzerland during pregnancy [91]; it described that some women reported not having had a choice about their birthing process. The women thought that the medical providers may have been unfamiliar in dealing with patients with SCIs or else felt anxious about it. A medical chart review study could add more insight into this theme.

Women described several medical complications and how they dealt with. Remarkably they did not describe or name the phenomenon of autonomic dysreflexia (AD) which is a common and severe complication during labour in SCI patients [64]. We would like to point out, however, that this study reports the subjective perspective of the women experiencing medical complications. By not mentioning some medical needs does not mean that they are not important or do not occur. Contrary, this may reflect the high competence of the care deliverer, taking risks into account without unsettling women during the birth process. Since we report retrospective data, we assume that women remembered rather medical needs during pregnancy course than during birth. Despite the lack of AD in our SCI population, the reader should not assume that the danger does not exist. Practitioners managing labor in SCI women still need to be acutely aware of the possibility of AD and also be well-versed in treating potential paroxysmal cardiovascular instability.

In summary, our findings demonstrate that pregnancy in women with SCIs may lead to medical problems. Patients with SCIs frequently use medications on a permanent basis, such as for pain, spasticity, or bladder management. Although these drugs may not be licensed for use during pregnancy, no major complications due to alterations in medication were reported. According to our data, bladder management during pregnancy seems to be a major issue but it was manageable for all women without irreversible complications. It is noteworthy that many possible complications, such as DVT or pressure sores, did not occur. This may indicate that providing adequate education to patients in primary rehabilitation leads to low complication rates due to sufficient self-care, even in “high risk” situations.

STUDY LIMITATIONS

The comparably small number of participants is a limitation of this study. No official register exists of women with SCI who gave birth in Switzerland. We had to rely on the SwiSCI cohort study and recruiting directly in the disability community with the help of our study participants. This variation allowed us to recruit all over the country, but still we do not have a firm ground to make statements regarding the representativeness of our sample.

Furthermore, the questionnaire specifically mentioned possible medical complications, whereas other possible complications were not mentioned. With an open question at the end of the questionnaire the women had the possibility to mention further complications. In addition, the questionnaire was not validated, meaning we do not have data on the accuracy of these women's retrospective accounts with regard to medical complications or interventions during pregnancy. The complications indicated were typical of the most frequent medical problems reported during pregnancy. For us, it was important to assess whether these problems did occur in the survey participants. Even more significantly, we wanted to determine how the women coped with these problems. Additionally, any significant, far-reaching complications may have a higher likelihood of being remembered.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of our study clearly demonstrate that although medical complications are not infrequent during pregnancy in women with SCIs, pregnancy and delivery in this group of women is possible without posing an intolerable risk to the mothers or the children. Urologic problems seem to be the most frequent complications experienced during pregnancy.

PERCEIVED SERVICE NEEDS
OF MOTHERS WITH SPINAL CORD INJURY

Perceived needs and experiences with healthcare services of women with spinal cord injury during pregnancy and childbirth – a qualitative content analysis of focus groups and individual interviews

Bertschy S, Geyh S, Pannek J, Meyer T, BMC Health Services Research, 2015, 15:234.

ABSTRACT

Background: Women after a spinal cord injury (SCI), who decide to get pregnant and to become mothers, have special health care service needs. This study aims to identify the perceived service needs of woman with SCI during pregnancy and childbirth in Switzerland and to reconstruct their experiences of healthcare service utilization based on their accounts.

Methods: A qualitative content analysis based on focus groups and individual interviews was conducted. 17 mothers with SCI who had given birth following SCI within the past 15 years participated. The data were transcribed verbatim before content analyses were carried out. Primary data was collected from August 2012 to September 2013 at the Swiss Paraplegic Research Centre, Nottwil; the University of Lausanne and at the homes of the participants.

Results: Mothers reported a broad spectrum of medical needs, including the need for access to improved integrated care. They also reported difficulties finding providers with knowledge of both rehabilitation medicine (i.e. spinal cord medicine) and gynaecology. Mothers preferred using local health care services and regular birth hospitals, and reported receiving no additional benefit from the services of specialised SCI centres during pregnancy. A pre-existing provider-patient relationship was helpful for optimizing care processes.

Conclusion: This study showed that pregnant women with SCI have various perceived healthcare needs and health care service use. Effective programs to improve these women's access to integrated care during pregnancy and childbirth and policies requiring the provision of specific pregnancy information and pre-birth services are necessary.

INTRODUCTION

A woman's desire to bear children often does not disappear after she has sustained a spinal cord injury (SCI), and women hoping to become mothers after a SCI have special health care service needs [82, 103], including accessibility of health care facilities, adjustment of assistive devices, counselling and changes in medications. Several qualitative studies from the United States (US) [33, 34, 104, 105] suggest that the needs of these women are often not fully met.

Although pregnancy outcomes seem to be favourable after SCI [69, 101, 106], women with disabilities may face problems during pregnancy and childbirth due to physical barriers, lack of specialised services, health care system issues, and communicational, informational and attitudinal barriers [19, 21]. Health care providers have also described difficulties in service provision for women with disabilities during pregnancy and childbirth from their perspectives [23, 63, 78, 107, 108]. The limited knowledge available about pregnancy and childbirth after SCI has been poorly disseminated to stakeholders, including women with SCI. Most of these women report that they did not receive adequate information before becoming pregnant [64].

Previous studies have shown that it is important to meet the needs of pregnant women with SCI to ensure optimal health of the mother and child, to ensure participation and quality of life, to ensure equity of service provision and to avoid discrimination [20, 21, 38, 52, 58, 103, 109-111].

The United Nation's *Convention for the Rights of People with Disabilities* (Art. 25) [112] emphasizes the right to best health care services and explicitly stresses the relevance of sexual and reproductive health. The World Health Organization also launched a program to promote reproductive health among people with disabilities [112, 113]. In the context of the health care rights of people with disabilities, SCI can serve as a case in point illustrating the concerns of women with physical disabilities during pregnancy and childbirth.

However, research on reproductive health care services for women with SCI is scarce. Current reviews of the literature reveal a focus on physical and other barriers [114]. These studies also lament the disparities in obtaining reproductive health care services [21] among women with disabilities, including women with SCI, especially in North America. In addition, the research has documented health risks and secondary complications during pregnancy and childbirth in women with SCI [38, 68-70, 109]. A clinical practice guideline edited by a consortium for spinal cord medicine in the US summarized the existing medical evidence on fertility, birth control, pregnancy, labour, delivery and menopause in women with SCI [115]. However, the guideline

depicts the professional perspective, and there is a lack of sufficient knowledge on health care needs from the perspectives of women with SCI who are pregnant or planning a pregnancy.

Therefore, an increased understanding of the use of health care services during pregnancy and childbirth after SCI is required to optimize available services [37, 38]. Several questions have arisen requiring answers, including: *Which services are needed, provided and used? Why and with which result? To what degree are the services tailored to the perceived needs of the pregnant women? What constitutes a good health care experience for pregnant women with SCI?*

The aims of this paper are to identify the perceived service needs of woman with SCI during pregnancy and childbirth in Switzerland and to reconstruct their experiences of healthcare service utilization based on their accounts.

METHODS

STUDY DESIGN

In order to identify the perceived service needs of woman with SCI during pregnancy and childbirth and to reconstruct their experiences of healthcare service utilization we used an open, qualitative research design. Women's accounts on their health care experiences were elicited in focus groups and, in addition, in individual interviews. Both data from focus groups and interviews were transcribed verbatim. The transcripts were analysed using qualitative content analysis [116], an inductive coding approach wide-spread in the German health research [117]. This approach was chosen because it is suitable to analyse how women interpret and make meaning from their health care experiences and to interpret their accounts in lights of potential unmet service needs.

PARTICIPANTS

Participants characteristics were aligned with the Swiss spinal cord injury cohort study (SwiSCI) [81]. We included 18–55-year-old mothers diagnosed with traumatic or non-traumatic SCI, who were permanent residents in Switzerland and gave birth after the injury within the past 15 years. Individuals with congenital conditions leading to paraplegia or tetraplegia were excluded: spina bifida, sclerosis and

amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, and Guillan-Barre' syndrome. We used different pathways to recruit potential participants. Mothers were recruited through the Swiss Spinal Cord Injury Cohort (SwiSCI) [81] database and through snowball sampling in the disability community [92]. Both lists were matched and all 94 names were cross-checked. We excluded seven duplicates, three Italian speaking mothers and 24 women over 55 years of age. The remaining 60 eligible women received information about the study aims, the study procedures and a response card to indicate their willingness to participate. The response rate was 70% (42 women). These respondents were contacted by telephone for a second eligibility check. Of these mothers, 18 did not meet the eligibility criteria and seven declined to participate. Seventeen mothers expressed interest in taking part in the study, representing a final response rate of 28%. The recruitment of the study participants is illustrated in Figure 2.

FIGURE 2 Recruitment of study participants

DATA COLLECTION

Focus groups and individual interviews were conducted. The original aim was to assemble the women for group discussions; however, many women asked for individual interviews because of organizational, personal and language (German/French) concerns. Four focus groups and five individual interview sessions were held. The interviews were moderated by the principle investigator, supported by one assistant. The principle investigator was a wheelchair-user woman who encouraged the women to describe their experiences with health care providers and services. She sought to provide an open atmosphere to allow participants to share personal experiences. The pilot-test revealed that more serious discussions typically emerged after about one hour of interaction. Therefore we chose small groups to activate the discussions [118]. Focus groups took place at the Swiss Paraplegic Research Centre in Nottwil, at the University of Lausanne, and individual interviews were done at the participants' homes. The focus group sessions were approximately 120–180 minutes, and the individual interviews were approximately 45–60 minutes. The interviews were semi-structured and guided by previously developed key questions [119]. The key questions were formulated based on a theoretical model of health services use [120], review of the literature and expert knowledge. The interview guideline was pilot-tested with a focus group of four mothers who did not match the eligibility criteria and who had given birth more than 15 years prior.

The participants were asked about their experiences during pregnancy and childbirth. Experiences included details regarding professional support providers, the types of care these professional provided, which providers offered care for which problems, whether the women felt to have received appropriate support for their health care needs, their satisfaction with the information received and suggestions for improved care in the future (Appendix 3).

Participants received a demographic questionnaire (Appendix 2) and an informed consent form, which they completed and signed before the interview. On two occasions, two different mothers brought their children to the focus group session. The study drop-out rate was zero. The interview sessions were held in the Swiss German or French languages, were electronically voice-recorded and were transcribed with f4 software for data analysis. The study was approved by the ethics committee of the Canton Lucerne on 27 April 2012 (project number 12027).

ANALYSES

THEORETICAL MODEL

The study and qualitative content analyses were informed by the behavioural model of health services utilisation by Andersen [120], which is one of the most widely used frameworks in health services research regarding service utilisation [121] (Figure 3).

The model comprises four domains: environmental factors, population characteristics, health behaviour and health outcomes. Environmental factors related to policy and health system determinants that describe the context of service use. Population characteristics include a number of predisposing factors that determine the use of health services. These include the individual's predisposition to obtain services and the perceived or normative need for these services. Health behaviour is expressed within the contexts of individual health practices and the use of health services. Health outcome dimensions describe perceived and evaluated health status and consumer satisfaction.

FIGURE 3 Model of health care services utilization [120] p. 8

ANALYSIS PROCESS

We used content analysis [116, 122] to structure the transcribed interview materials. Our approach was to utilise the women's reports of health service experiences to determine service needs and use of services. Our conceptual approach was based on Andersen's behavioural model. We created a coding scheme with main categories derived deductively from the Andersen model [120]. The main categories were 1) women's perceived health needs and 2) the health services used. The sub-categories were derived inductively from the data. Inductive coding was used to ensure that our analyses comprehensively represented the content communicated by the participants. The categories were ordered within a taxonomy, where each category received a specific definition. The codes were developed successively and were revised or deleted and new codes added as the analyses proceeded.

RIGOR

A number of steps were taken to ensure the trustworthiness of this qualitative study. *Confirmability* [123] was ensured by including various researchers during the analysis process. Two researchers participated in developing the codes, conducting the coding and the taxonomy. The first author completed the initial coding and met with the second author regularly to discuss emergent themes and alternate interpretations to guide further analyses. The main coder completed all transcripts and compared the results in determined sections with the co-coder until a common coding was established. Thoughts and consensus solutions were summarized in a separate report sheet.

Credibility [123] was enhanced through the involvement of all co-authors at different stages of the study. The main investigator and the second author formulated the interview questions, developed the coding scheme and analysed and interpreted the data. During these steps, the researchers met regularly with the senior author. The other contributor conducted a critical revision of the manuscript for important intellectual content. The research team members possessed expertise in health service research, psychology, medicine and living with an SCI.

Transferability [123] of the results was enhanced by the inclusion of women with different lesions and education levels who had given birth during different periods within the 15 years prior, therefore covering the bandwidth of the study period. Within the results description, we attempted to display the different experiences in their heterogeneity.

RESULTS

PARTICIPANTS' CHARACTERISTICS

The participants included 17 mothers, including one pregnant woman with SCI¹. The average age at the time of delivery of the first child following SCI was 33 years. All the women were married or in stable relationships at the time of their pregnancies. They had high levels of education and most were employed. Nearly half of the women worked in health care contexts as nurses, nutritionists, pharmacists, psychologists or life coaches for disabled people. Most were rehabilitated in SCI centres if their injuries occurred in adulthood. Those injured as children were rehabilitated in children's hospitals. All names in the manuscript are pseudonyms and stated in Table 5.

¹ Due to the small number of participants who meet the inclusion criteria, we included in the study a woman pregnant in the third trimester who had experiences with the care system.

Pseudonym	Age by Interview	Marital status by interview	Number of children before SCI	Number of children after SCI	TSI (y) at birth of 1st child	SCI level	Education	Education years	Working	Interview
Emma	39	Married	0	1	19	Para incompl.	Apprenticeship / Training	15	yes	FG 1
Anna	41	Married	0	1	22	Para compl.	Apprenticeship / Training	12	yes	FG 1
Lea	32	partnership	0	0	pregnant	Tetra incompl.	Undergrad or college degree	14	yes	FG 1
Emily	50	Married	1	1	7	Para compl.	Post graduate	23	yes	FG 2
Lilly	49	Married	0	2	14	Para incompl.	Undergrad or college degree	19	yes	FG 2
Sara	44	Married	0	2	3	Para compl.	Apprenticeship / Training	12	yes	FG 2
Marie	45	Married	0	2	7	Tetra compl.	Undergrad or college degree	17	yes	FG 2
Amelie	34	Married	0	1	11	Para incompl.	Apprenticeship / Training	12	no	FG 3
Lina	38	Married	0	2	17	Para compl.	Post graduate	18	yes	FG 3
Maya	45	Divorced	0	1	5	Para compl.	Highschool	8	yes	FG 3
Claudia	47	Married	0	2	15	Para compl.	Apprenticeship / Training	12	no	EI 5
Rachel	43	partnership	1	1	2	Para incompl.	Undergrad or college degree	17	yes	EI 4
Laura	32	Single	0	1	2	Para incompl.	Undergrad or college degree	15	no	EI 1
Margrit	45	Married	0	2	13	Tetra incompl.	Apprenticeship / Training	13	yes	FG 4
Jeannine	30	Married	0	2	24	Para compl.	Undergrad or college degree	21	yes	FG 4
Monika	48	partnership	0	1	19	Para incompl.	Undergrad or college degree	19	yes	EI 2
Kathrin	44	Single	0	1	15	Tetra incompl.	Apprenticeship / Training	17	yes	EI 3

TSI = time since injury

TABLE 5: Participants demographics

PERCEIVED SERVICE NEEDS DURING PREGNANCY

We learned from the participating women that pregnancy after SCI required extended and tailored health care services. The women's reports about their perceived needs were grouped into six categories: (1) perceived need for information about SCI and pregnancy; (2) perceived need for specific health professionals' expertise; (3) perceived need for medical treatment; (4) perceived need for access to and availability of care facilities; (5) perceived need for specific supplies and equipment and (6) perceived need for improved integration of care.

PERCEIVED NEED FOR INFORMATION ABOUT SCI AND PREGNANCY

The participating mothers reported having had questions regarding the interdependence of SCI and pregnancy. *'What is different in my situation?'* was the driving question behind their quests for information.

Besides medical questions, I had a lot of practical questions, like 'Do I feel the child at all?' —Laura

During my first appointment with the gynaecologist, I asked him if he had other patients like me before and if he knew the process. He told me: 'No not at all.' He said he could find out, but that he thought there was no problem. Then I said, 'Yeah, but how am I going to give birth? And what will happen?' I had a thousand questions besides all the standard questions of a standard pregnancy. Then he told me: 'Well, we will see. I think you're not a high-risk pregnancy.' He said: 'We'll frame it as a normal pregnancy, and if you need monthly controls, we will do that, no problem.' So, that was strange. —Jeannine

PERCEIVED NEED FOR SPECIFIC HEALTH PROFESSIONALS' EXPERTISE

Women reported having had a desire for providers with obstetrical as well as rehabilitation medicine expertise. The lack of provider knowledge about the comprehensive needs of women with SCI during pregnancy spanned a range of themes. How to treat SCI-related conditions, how to distinguish between SCI-related and non-SCI-related conditions and how to evaluate treatments were perceived as difficult to handle.

... I prefer a good gynaecologist who reads a little in the SCI literature. —Anna

What profit is rehabilitation medicine knowledge if the doctor has no idea about neonatology? —Amelie

That was principally the most difficult question: Where are the knowledgeable people? Where are the top people? Only through asking friends I came to learn of this gynaecologist in the area. —Laura

An existing relationship with a provider with knowledge of the SCI history was perceived by the women as helpful and was presented as a key issue in provider trust and continuance of care with the provider.

My doctor said he would be confident in treating me. I was glad I did not had to change providers because we knew each other already and I trusted him. —Anna

The education programs (e.g. pregnancy or other preparatory birth courses) were seen as inadequate. The women reported that the courses were not tailored to their needs and, therefore, were not utilised.

It bothered me to go. I did not want to go... I was not interested in these types of courses. —Margrit

My doctor told me that it was useless for me because I would not give birth in a natural way. —Jeannine

PERCEIVED NEED FOR MEDICAL TREATMENT

Women required medical treatment for issues with health and functioning. Their pregnancies exacerbated pre-existing functional difficulties, such as urinary tract infections (UTIs), spasticity and bowel problems. Pregnancy-related problems, including preeclampsia, pre- or postpartum symptoms or complaints e.g., signs of pre-term delivery, pre-term gravidity pain before calculated birth time and/or antepartum bleeding, post-term bleeding, infection and/or pain led to needs for medical treatments.

I also had problems with the bowel, but the bladder was probably worse, I think. I noticed the difference with the bladder and the bowel was more constipated. — Rachel

I used self-medication, but always consulted my doctor [general practitioner] first, since I knew immediately when I had one [bladder infection]. — Margrit

PERCEIVED NEED FOR ACCESS TO AND AVAILABILITY OF SERVICES

Participating women reported having had different experiences with the availability and accessibility of facilities, providers and educational programs. Women also revealed the special problem of not being able to identify or find SCI-knowledgeable providers or institutions. A woman described her difficulties finding a gynaecologist:

...I'm always afraid when I have to look for a provider... there is no elevator, no parking and heavy doors. —Emma

...we looked for a gynaecologist who had a wheelchair-accessible practice, which is in many places not the case. —Maya

I completely gave up looking for a knowledgeable provider. I had maybe not that much pressure because I had the feeling that I could do it by my own. Then I also did not insist too long searching for this one [gynaecologist with expertise in SCI]. There was definitely nobody who somehow had an idea about the topic or to provide information. I would not swear, but I could not remember having talked with anyone. —Lilly

PERCEIVED NEED FOR SPECIFIC SUPPLIES AND EQUIPMENT

The women reported that inappropriately equipped facilities made examinations, diagnostics and hospital stays difficult and that very few facilities had the necessary equipment.

It would certainly have been good to have a place where the whole infrastructure was available: an examination chair, enough space and rooms to fit our needs. —Laura

A lot of important equipment and tools were missing in the clinic. My husband had to bring almost our whole household to my room. —Marie

For intimacy and privacy reasons, the women reported having preferred to stay alone rather than to share a room with able-bodied mothers.

Due to my specific needs... I found it embarrassing to explain to my room neighbour how my intimate care works. —Lina

PERCEIVED NEED FOR IMPROVED INTEGRATION OF CARE

Poor integrated care influenced women's satisfaction with the care process. Since experts with holistic knowledge were unavailable, the women felt responsible to find knowledgeable providers for their care needs, which was inconvenient and disappointing to them.

I would have appreciated a gynaecologist who had more experience with patients with SCI, who knew more about the bladder, all the hormones and bowel management. I sometimes ran desperately from one place to another... looking for a place where I could ask my questions and receiving answers... but not being able to consult the neurologists and the urologists and so on. But maybe that's our destiny... that we will always have to see different providers. —Laura

In addition, if participating women described different health behaviours, the need for comprehensive and continuous care as it would be provided with interdisciplinary provider teams was present. Some women would have appreciated to receive services from one site. The other group called for centralized or cooperative support services. Important for both groups was that their medical concerns were taken seriously.

They [hospital staff] did not talk to each other. In the hospital of my home city, they filled in my medical chart with whatever they wanted. Every time, I had to re-explain my story and all my problems related to my pregnancy. —Jeannine

WHICH HEALTH SERVICES WERE USED?

The use of health care services was reported based on the involved health professional groups and facilities and the perceived degrees of service usage. The women's experiences with health services differed in service choice, service variety and the number of services used.

VISITED HEALTH PROFESSIONALS

Several women said that as soon as they believed they were pregnant, they felt an urgency to make appointments with their gynaecologists.

As I realized that I was pregnant, immediately I wanted to visit my gynaecologist. He said I should come only after 5 weeks, because before then we would not see anything anyway. —Amelie

In cases where the pregnancy course was uncomplicated, the women did not require additional medical care or monitoring. Regular gynaecological pregnancy monitoring included blood analyses, blood pressure monitoring, vaginal examinations, urine samples and foetal heart rate monitoring. The women reported having visited various health care providers, including general physicians, emergency physicians, urologists, neurologists and internists, when the pregnancy course was complicated by issues, such as hypertension, cardiovascular problems, UTIs, pneumonia or obstetric

concerns. For treating specific SCI-related symptoms, women initially consulted their gynaecologists and, in some cases, a rehabilitation medicine doctor or urologist with SCI knowledge. Latter consultations occurred in SCI outpatient settings. Women with incomplete lesions reported re-experiencing moments of anxiety and fear of functional limitations for which they required psychological counselling. One woman described her fear of re-experiencing loss of sensation in her legs:

I can move [incomplete paralysis], so it was only psychological for me to go through that experience [epidural anesthesia] again of losing the feelings, the sensation and movement, and not knowing if it would come back again. ... Every week I saw a psychologist and talked about how I felt. I did some relaxation and breathing exercises and just... it was just a session for me to say these are my worries, this is how I feel, and he had good advice for me; this really helped. —Rachel

The women also reported using complementary and alternative medicine services, such as naturopathy. One woman engaged a professional support person:

It was important to me to have a person outside of us who knew my specific needs, too. I hired a woman as coach to support us. My husband told her things like, 'my wife cannot lay on a hard surface' and things like that. She was present during my birth. That gave me confidence. —Lilly

Most of the expectant women found the support of experienced mothers helpful. They discussed personal issues, such as increasing belly size, incontinence or partnership issues, as well as which service facilities might be most helpful to address specific problems. The women reported that these encounters helped them become more comfortable with their pregnancies and reduced their fears about the upcoming deliveries. A woman described her appreciation:

...what does it actually mean being pregnant and to give birth? What is possible? Those were my relevant questions. So the greatest help was certainly Monica [experienced mother], with her own experiences and her knowledge about where to get information. —Laura

CONSULTED FACILITIES

The women expressed desires for detailed information about pregnancy and SCI. In their attempts to meet these needs, the expectant mothers reported having consulted the internet or having contacted SCI rehabilitation centres. Their contacts with the centres left the women feeling frustrated because their expectations were not met. One woman explained:

I'm so excited about the bundled knowledge in this SCI centre. I think that's such a good way to care for this population, as it takes place there. But the

pregnancy area has been excluded, and that was very disappointing for me.
—Lilly

I researched a little bit on the Internet. But even there, there is very, very poor information, almost nothing. —Lina

Only one mother described having received a consultation hour with an external consultant gynaecologist in an SCI institution.

She [gynaecologist] comes to the SCI centre [X] every month or couple of months to see women who would like to have children and to discuss any problems or any issues. I wanted to see her first, because I had some questions about what it meant —would it be a problem to have a child after the SCI —and to get some advice. —Rachel

Inpatient stays in university or regional hospitals occurred mostly in emergency situations, such as those involving bladder problems with severe complications, pre-delivery symptoms or symptoms after a fall. In emergency settings, women described different types of difficulties in care continuity and reported lack of efficiency compared to outpatient settings. The women reported that most treatment difficulties were encountered in bladder and anaesthesia complications. From the women's perspectives, unfamiliarity in treating patients with a SCI led to inefficient treatments, unnecessary diagnostic tests and some unsafe treatment choices.

I would like to mention that I was completely satisfied with my gynaecologist. But the fact that I had been in the hospital afterwards, and the assistant doctors were visiting me there... [...] I remember a few scenes where they over-examined me. As my breasts were under the computer tomographer, I almost dismissed myself from the hospital. I started to argue with the doctor, because I felt this was leading nowhere. —Lina

The women expressed different ideas of what a birth hospital should offer for women with SCI. Those with uncomplicated pregnancy courses tended to use birth hospitals in their home areas, while women with difficult pregnancy courses or with higher health literacy looked for well-reputed, nearby regional or university hospitals with neonatal units.

...more important for me was that, if then something would have happened, they could take the baby and go only down the street and not drive through half of the city to bring the baby to the hospital with a neonatology department. —Anna

Beside the available medical facilities for giving birth, the women reported having requested alternative options and described particular dissatisfaction with birthing houses. None of the participants gave birth in such an institution. Some of the women reported feeling somewhat unwelcomed in these institutions and described obvious apprehensiveness among the providers towards handling the pregnancy of a woman with an SCI. One woman described:

I just wanted to have a look at this option (birthing centre) and they said that if the child remained hung with his shoulders during birth, I would have to immediately get out of the bathtub and transfer quickly to the birthing chair. If people like me needed help getting out of the bathtub — because I could not do it alone — that would be complicated. Also, they said you do not know how far the birth process is. If the head is already coming out, then I could not sit on the wheelchair and they would have to carry me over. That would be a risk. —Lea

Some of the women with an incomplete lesion made use of the possibility to learn pre-birth pelvic floor exercises and a woman after child loss was grateful to visit a special remission course. However, some of the women, especially with a complete lesion were unconcerned, because a caesarean section was planned or they thought the courses were not tailored to their needs.

I'm in a remission course for women after child loss. The exchange is different for women in difficult situations. —Laura

The pelvic floor exercises that were shown in the first course, I certainly could not do them (laughs). Yeah, I didn't see the purpose of continuing the birth preparation course once it was clear that I would have a caesarean section. I did not need more breathing exercises (laughs). —Claudia

PERCEIVED DEGREE OF HEALTH SERVICES UTILISATION

Women judged their impressions of the pregnancies of able-bodied women in relation to their assumptions about these and their own pregnancies, and reported experiencing care very differently. The women with SCI reported having felt that they were seen more often by their gynaecologists, especially by the end of the third trimester.

I saw my gynaecologist every two weeks and I had an ultrasound examination, which is not the case for all women. Given my situation, he acted very paternalistic. —Monica

In the beginning, I had a 6-week interval, and now I'm beginning the 7th month and we see each other every fifth week for controls. This is certainly something that is probably different for other women, unless they have a risky pregnancy. —Lea

However, some women reported having felt that their care experiences were equal to those of able-bodied women.

I think that I had fewer consultations than my other girlfriends who had been with another doctor. Today's consultations are handled different. My doctor was experienced. —Lina

Women reported that they were required to visit different providers to solve their health problems. They also mentioned that they were more likely hospitalized when the complications were not clear and that their hospital stays were longer.

After being declared as a 'risk pregnancy' — I do not know what this word means — but risk means different. So I was treated differently. I think that's why I stayed 10 days in the hospital. In general, it is rare that somebody has to stay 10 days there. —Kathrin

DISCUSSION

This study sheds light on subjective service needs and the utilization of health services during pregnancy and childbirth of women with SCI in Switzerland.

Previous medical, disability and health service studies in other countries [19, 68, 69, 106, 109] have shown that pregnant women with SCI develop specific health care needs and face challenges obtaining services and specific treatments. Medical studies [68, 69, 101] have identified needs related to body functions, such as UTIs, autonomic dysfunction, skin breakdown and respiratory complications, whereas other studies [19, 63, 106] have reported environmental, structural and procedural needs (e.g. architectural barriers, unfamiliar providers or no coordination of care). This study identified the full bandwidth of health care needs of women during pregnancy and childbirth.

Reproductive health services are in Switzerland for women sufficiently accessible and available. The density of gynaecologists is lower in the countryside than in urban areas, general practitioners and family doctors overtake also the obstetric part and cover a wider range of activities than their urban counterparts [7]. Though, the obstetric health service supply in Switzerland is satisfactory for able-bodied pregnant women [124]. There seems to be no research examining the accessibility to health services for disabled persons in Switzerland. In this study, women with SCI appear to be impacted by environmental barriers to health services during the perinatal phase. Access to public buildings (e.g., hospitals, schools, public buildings) is regulated in Switzerland since 2002 [125]. This law is only applicable to newly built or renovated public buildings and regulates access to and not the accommodation in facilities and does not include private buildings (e.g., private practices). Therefore a comfortable utilization for women with a disability of those facilities is not guaranteed which is also reflected in our results.

The women strongly emphasized their desires for expanded availability of providers with both pregnancy and SCI knowledge to provide wider service choices. Although this may not be possible in all settings, particularly in more rural areas, increasing the

number of knowledgeable providers may improve these women's likelihood of seeking needed care.

In Switzerland 94 % of the women give birth in a medical facility (hospital) and 6% choose a birthing house or a birth at home as alternative solution. Traditionally no doctor is present in birthing houses and the birth is entirely handled by the midwife and the woman. The study results showed that women who were interested in this option were disappointed through the health professionals' attitude to preferably refuse care for disabled women.

Participating women preferred to conduct the perinatal consultations in their home areas and only a few women requested counselling mainly for medication issues from specialised SCI settings. This could mean that those women who only used services in their home areas may not have known about or available counselling services in specialised SCI settings. Advertised and specialised and pregnancy counselling, as described in Tebbet's work [82], may increase women's self-confidence during pregnancy and reduce their dissatisfaction with the services offered at SCI centres.

The women communicated an elevated need for information about greater risks for secondary complications, pre-term births and caesarean deliveries, as reported in prior literature [62, 126, 127], which was also substantiated in this study. These perceptions highlight the challenges women may face when seeking needed services and being cared for by unfamiliar providers. These women's perspectives also point to the critical need for more comprehensive services. Related to this need is the necessity for interdisciplinary cooperative networking not only for pregnant women with SCI but also for women with SCI planning to have children. Health care seeking could be addressed through regionally designated health professionals trained in providing perinatal care for these patients. In addition, a medical hotline could improve the effectiveness of care, and exchanges with experienced mothers may provide additional guidance. This exchange of experience could be provided in the form of a website for women with SCI, such as the Swedish project 'sciparenting.com' [128], which aims to provide information and knowledge about fertility, pregnancy, childbirth and parenting for persons with SCI. Tebbet [82] highlighted the positive experiences among women who participated in peer mentoring. Our study results also underlined this positive exchange, for which women reported to have a major impact in reducing anxiety and fear.

Lack of pre-birth counselling during pregnancy has also been identified in previous research [104, 129]. Burns [107] assumed in his survey that, with appropriate follow-up and care, women with SCI could be expected to maintain good gynaecologic health and deliver healthy children with minimal complications. However, the women in our study reported low rates of pre-birth education, showing the great need for pre-birth plans coordinating all involved parties. We suggest to include in this plan a checklist with information for women at each stage of pregnancy: a medical chart with

information about medication and bladder management (facilitates caesarean), and X-rays of the spinal cord, if available (important for administering anaesthesia).

It was interesting to note that the participating women tended to possess distinctive preconditions, which in some cases facilitated access to health services. Participating women tended to be highly educated, living in stable relationships, were socially integrated and seemed to be well informed about health issues. The question arises, then, if the women with SCI who decide to become mothers are different from women with SCI who do not desire to have children. This question should be further investigated in relation to epidemiological predictors.

Balancing SCI health care needs with available supply developed for able-bodied pregnant women may be a source of tension for some gynaecologists and SCI health care providers. The lacks of comprehensive knowledge, cooperation and regulations may also cause confusion, as specific guidelines in Switzerland have not been implemented in one field. Tailored information for women and providers should emphasize the availability of services to prevent mistreatment, under-treatment and over-treatment.

During the pregnancy course women have general or special medical needs. Study participants desired a medical treatment that took their special needs into account and at the same time they wished to be treated on the personal level in the professional-patient relationship as any other woman, i.e. without being discriminated on the grounds of their disability.

Women mentioned several medical complications, interestingly they did not describe or name the phenomena of autonomic dysreflexia, which is a common complication during the pregnancy course and birth process. We would like to point out, that this study reports the subjective perspective of the women how they experienced their need and use of healthcare. By not mentioning some for the reader evident or necessary medical needs doesn't mean that they are not important. Contrary, this may uncover the existing gaps and missing medical knowledge which should be transferred to the women.

STUDY LIMITATIONS

Our findings are based on a self-selected sample; therefore, there is question as to whether the results reflect a selection bias in participant characteristics. As we included mothers with different lesion levels, paraplegia as well as tetraplegia, our results relate to women with SCI of childbearing age. Due to the different natures (medical and social) of other disabilities, however, we cannot be certain of a broader transferability of the findings to other disability groups.

The rather unusually small number of participants within the focus groups was, in our experience, not obstructive for obtaining responses. Rather, it allowed a relaxed and intimate interaction of respondents and stimulated a rich discussion including new and valuable thoughts and ideas. The participants in the individual interviews had more difficulties talking openly and required more time and empathy from the interviewer [118]. It has been reported that persons feel more open to share personal experience in homogenous group discussions compared to individual interviews.

Due to the differences in social welfare systems and medical health systems, it might be problematic to compare our results with those of other countries. Therefore, comparisons between countries focusing on the factors influencing service use would be beneficial. Interestingly, despite the differences between the social and medical systems of the countries, we did observe results compatible with the international literature.

Based on the aims of our study we used the Andersen model as a frame of reference to guide our interview questions and analysis. However, this approach might have influenced our openness to experiences women made during pregnancy and childbirth.

The data were analysed with a qualitative approach (a summative evaluative approach was not applicable). We had to rely on the openness and memories of the mothers for data collection in these retrospective accounts. Therefore, in the future, a prospective study with a follow-up of women with SCI at child bearing age or who are pregnant would be helpful.

CONCLUSION

This study highlights several barriers that women with SCI face during pregnancy and childbirth. The existing health care services are far from being tailored to meet the needs and expectations of these mothers, and further improvements in both policy and practice are necessary to provide better health care to these women. Policy should provide a framework for health care providers that would allow them to most effectively meet the women's needs. There is a high demand for specialised antenatal services that are more client centred, offering specific information, peer support or increased accessibility and availability of services. Further research is recommended to understand which factors most influence service use, to characterize the women with SCI who choose to become mothers and to examine the providers' perspectives on accompanying women with SCI through pregnancy.

**EXPERIENCES OF HEALTHCARE PROVIDERS
IN DELIVERING MATERNITY CARE**

Delivering care under uncertainty: Swiss providers' experiences in caring for women with spinal cord injury during pregnancy and childbirth - an expert interview study,

Bertschy S, Pannek J, Meyer T, BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth, 2016, 16:181.

ABSTRACT

Background: When different health problems such as pregnancy and spinal cord injury (SCI) occur together, providing adequate care becomes even more challenging. Women with SCI may encounter a variety of specific problems and symptoms during pregnancy and childbirth, including urinary tract infections, pressure ulcers, constipation, autonomic dysreflexia, and preterm labour. Therefore, expertise from different medical specialties, especially spinal cord medicine and gynaecology. What is totally normal for experts of one specialty could cause a problem for experts from another specialty. Therefore, this study aimed to reconstruct the perceptions and experiences of healthcare providers in Switzerland in caring for women with SCI during pregnancy and childbirth.

Methods: The perception and experience of healthcare professionals toward providing care for women with SCI during pregnancy and labour were elicited using qualitative expert interviews and analysed using grounded theory techniques. Fifteen health professionals were interviewed, including gynaecologists (n=4), midwives (n=3), physical medicine and rehabilitation professionals (n=4), urologists (n=3), and a peer counsellor (n=1).

Results: Care delivery experiences of health professionals could be described as a forced reaction to decision making under uncertainty. However, health professionals seemed to express three different attitudes while handling the situation: (i) protective concerned attitude, (ii) 'no-big-deal' attitude, or (iii) precautionary attitude. The applied strategies were influenced by the conditions of the healthcare system, policies in place, and health professionals' behaviours. Consequently, health professionals faced with uncertainty felt like actors in a fragmented treatment process and called for interdisciplinary collaborations.

Conclusions: Our findings highlight the diversity of perspectives among different healthcare professionals with respect to the approach to care and delivery services for pregnant women with SCI. A need for more specific services, information, guidance, and guidelines for health professionals caring for woman with SCI during pregnancy and childbirth was identified. We strongly recommend further research on the development of integrated care concepts as well as clinical studies for establishing a more profound knowledge base.

INTRODUCTION

An increasing number of women with SCI decide to become mothers. Approximately 14% of women with SCI in the US have children after their injury [43, 44]. Thus far, there are no records of the number of women who gave birth after SCI in Switzerland. Until today, becoming a mother with SCI is rare and knowledge in this field is relatively minimal [19, 20]. Therefore, healthcare for pregnant women with SCI is unique and requires special medical attention.

Pregnancy and childbirth in women with SCI can cause specific problems and symptoms, which can vary from woman to woman. For instance, clinical studies have documented an elevated risk of developing urinary tract infections, pressure ulcers, constipation, autonomic dysreflexia, and thrombosis [66, 68, 75, 91, 127, 130-132]. In addition, various obstetrical challenges, including preterm labour, unattended delivery, and premature births, may arise [38, 62, 69, 71]. Women with SCI usually take medications for chronic conditions such as spasms and bladder and bowel problems, or for pain management [68, 69, 115]. When different healthcare needs arise together such as in SCI patients who are pregnant, providing adequate care becomes even more demanding.

Studies with health professionals providing care for women with SCI during pregnancy and childbirth indicate a scarcity of relevant studies [104, 130, 133], missing recommendations based on clinical trials [43], little availability and accessibility of reproductive services [21, 35, 91, 114], and substantial deficits in interprofessional collaboration [91, 127, 134] to achieve successful pregnancies with healthy outcomes for the mother and child.

Providing care for those women requires a combined knowledge in gynaecology and SCI medicine. It seems that these distinct skills very rarely run together [91, 107]. Therefore, health professionals from different fields are usually involved in the care process. This requires a special approach toward collaboration and integration of care [43]. What is a completely normal approach for one specialisation, could cause a problem for the other specialisation, e.g., administering antibiotics, performing obstetric ultrasonography, or prescribing thrombosis prophylactics may have unintentional harmful effects in pregnant women with SCI. Thus, health care services need to integrate multiple professional perspectives [68, 101, 135].

Reproductive health services for able-bodied pregnant women in Switzerland are sufficiently accessible and available [124]. However, in a previous study we observed that women with SCI face various difficulties in accessing care and in finding care providers with knowledge of both specialities—spinal cord medicine and gynaecology. It seems that so far there is no specialised pregnancy counselling service. The lack of specific comprehensive knowledge, cooperation, and regulations may cause confusion, as specific guidelines in Switzerland have not been implemented in one field [91]. As described above, this could cause a source of tension for some reproductive and SCI health care providers.

The question of how professionals deal with these challenges remains. In this study, we aimed to reconstruct the perceptions and experiences of healthcare providers in caring for women with SCI during pregnancy and childbirth. Our goal was to identify possible deficiencies in healthcare services, pinpoint probable reasons for it, and suggest ways to overcome these challenges.

METHODS

STUDY DESIGN

Between May and September 2014, we conducted a study with health professionals from the healthcare communities and hospital settings in Switzerland. Semi-structured individual expert interviews [136] were conducted with health professionals from various specialisations who provided care for at least one woman with SCI during pregnancy and childbirth. The providers were recruited through a previous study in which mothers with SCI had provided the names of their treating health care provider during pregnancy [91] and snowballing in the medical community. For reasons of analysis, only German-speaking health care professionals were included.

While we could have restricted our analysis to summarize what the experts reported during interviews, during the course of our investigation, it became clear that it was worthwhile to develop a deeper understanding of these special healthcare situations. Therefore, we decided to reconstruct the experiences and perceptions of the healthcare providers and attempted to develop possible reasons for and consequences of their experiences. To achieve this, we resorted to analysis techniques developed within the framework of grounded theory

(GT) methodology [137] for gaining a deeper understanding of these challenges. Considering the sampling strategy, the GT methodology was only applied in the analysis section.

STUDY PARTICIPANTS AND RECRUITMENT

The study included German-speaking healthcare providers in Switzerland who treated at least one pregnant woman with SCI during her pregnancy or childbirth. In Switzerland, there is no registry or official list of care providers who offer such services. Therefore, we used information from a previous study with concerned mothers [91]. We identified six main professional groups who accompanied women with SCI during pregnancy and childbirth, and a selective sample [138] was obtained from these groups for data collection: gynaecologists, physical medicine and rehabilitation (PMRs) professionals, urologists, midwives, anaesthesiologists, and peer counsellors. We aimed to conduct 15 interviews, with no more than 5 interviews per healthcare provider group. A total of 35 potential participants were identified and 24 were contacted by email, phone, or in person. Due to reasons of language, double address, and no identification possible (unknown contact address), 11 health care providers were excluded. Of the 24 healthcare providers, 3 did not meet the inclusion criteria and 3 did not respond to our emails and phone calls. Of the remaining eligible sample of 18 healthcare providers, 3 refused to participate because of time constraints. Subsequently, 15 interviews were conducted with the following distribution of participants: 5 PMR professionals, 4 gynaecologists, 3 midwives, 2 urologists, and 1 peer counsellor (Figure 4).

We faced difficulties finding anaesthesiologists during data collection: either the mothers did not remember their anaesthesiologist's name or we were unable to find the anaesthesiologist's location. In every interview, we asked interviewees for further possible participants who matched the inclusion criteria. We also asked health professionals if they knew any anaesthesiologists involved in the care of SCI women during pregnancy and childbirth. Either they did not remember who was responsible for anaesthesia or the anaesthesiologist had left the hospital. Therefore, we excluded this group from the study. In Switzerland, the medical management of persons with SCI is mainly provided by PMR specialists; therefore, we did not include neurologists in our study.

FIGURE 4 RECRUITMENT OF PARTICIPANTS

Interviews were conducted in the form of semi-structured interviews, guided by previously developed key questions concerning their experiences with pregnant women with SCI, the main challenges they faced, how they gained their expertise in pregnancy with SCI, and how collaboration with other colleagues was performed or perceived. The full interview guide can be seen in the additional file in appendix 4.

All interviews were conducted by either the first author or a research assistant trained in qualitative research methods. Since the experts' jobs and busy schedules often led to time constraints if interviews were planned, we offered them the possibility of a phone interview if this was more suitable to their schedule. Nine participants opted for a phone interview, while the other six were interviewed at their workplace. The interview durations ranged from 16 to 51 minutes, with an average of 28 minutes.

Prior to the interview session, participants received study information and an invitation letter by email or post. At the interview session itself, the interviewer repeated information about study aim, procedure, and how the authors protected the anonymity and confidentiality of the participants. The participants had the right to withdraw from our study at any time. All participants' names were replaced with a pseudonym. Interviews were audio-taped, transcribed, and analysed verbatim in German. Responses that represented variation within each theme were selected from the transcripts for inclusion in this article and translated from German into English.

TABLE 6 STUDY PARTICIPANTS

<i>Groups</i>	<i>Setting</i>
Group 1 4 <i>Gynaecologist</i>	2 Primary Care Facility 1 Private Practice 1 District Hospital
Group 2 3 <i>Midwives</i>	2 Independent 1 Privat Practice
Group 3 5 <i>PMR professionals</i>	1 Outpatient Clinic 2 SCI Rehab Clinic 1 University Hospital 1 SCI Association
Group 4 2 <i>Urologists</i>	2 Outpatient Clinic
Group 5 1 <i>Peer counselor</i>	1 SCI Rehab Clinic

The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki [139]. The participants were informed about the aims of the research project and took part in the study voluntarily as part of their professional commitment. Oral informed consent was obtained and recorded before starting the interviews.

TABLE 8 PARTICIPANTS CHARACTERISTICS

Pseudonym	Function	Field of expertise	Setting	Experience with pregnant women with SCI
1	Matthias Gerber Senior physician	Gynaecology	District Hospital	Treatment of patients during pregnancy who have been sent to the hospital from the surrounding area and SCI centre; gained knowledge through interdisciplinary exchange of knowledge with colleagues and high interest in SCI; practice located close to an SCI centre; participates in workshops about sexuality with SCI.
2	Michael Brunner Chief resident	Urology	SCI Outpatient Clinic	Treatment of patients during pregnancy for the past 7 years; high competence in treating urological problems in SCI patients.
3	Anton Denner Online-Doctor	Spinal Cord Medicine / Internist	Paraplegic Association	Online consultations for SCI-related questions; no gynaecological knowledge.
4	Nicole Müller Senior physician	Spinal Cord Medicine / Internist	SCI Rehab Clinic	Treatment of 1 patient during pregnancy; longstanding experience in treating SCI patients; patient suffered from SCI right after getting pregnant; discussions about treatment with her team and the treating gynaecologist.
5	Martin Roggo Co-Chief resident	Gynaecology	Primary care facility	Treatment of 2 disabled patients during pregnancy; one doesn't depend on a wheelchair anymore.
6	Franziska Schneider Midwife	Midwife	Private Practice	Treatment of 1 patient during pregnancy and birth; work experience: 5 years.
7	Julia Peter Chief resident	Spinal Cord Medicine	University Hospital	Treated and accompanied 10 patients during pregnancy; longstanding experience in treating SCI patients; comparatively less expertise in gynaecology.
8	Barbara Senior physician	Spinal Cord	SCI Rehab Clinic	Treatment of several patients during pregnancy; last treatment of

Jung		Medicine		
				pregnant women with SCI was a couple of years ago.
9	Anna Weiss	Midwife	Midwife	Independent / Primary care facility Treatment of 1 patient during pregnancy; work experience: 13 years; wrote a thesis about pregnant women with SCI by interviewing 2 women with SCI.
10	Jasmin Rieger	Peer Counsellor	Peer counsellor	SCI Outpatient Clinic Accompanied patients during pregnancy as a peer, experienced pregnancy and SCI herself; works in an SCI environment; high interdisciplinary exchange with colleagues and other peers; conducts workshops on sexuality and SCI on a regular basis.
11	Katharina Bach	Midwife	Midwife	Independent Treatment of 1 patient during pregnancy; patient was a friend and she accompanied her mainly during puerperal visits and had some contact during pregnancy; work experience: 5 years; knows the SCI community well.
12	Elisabeth Frey	Chief resident	Gynaecology	Primary care facility Treatment of 5-10 patients during pregnancy; work experience : 30 years in larger clinics in Switzerland and other countries; gained knowledge about SCI through interdisciplinary exchange with colleagues and literature.
13	Georg Fischer	Head of SCI Outpatient Clinic	Spinal Cord Medicine	SCI Outpatient Clinic Accompanied patients during pregnancy; no knowledge in gynaecology; treated SCI-related problems and consulted patients and gynaecologists.
14	Alexander Brandt	Senior physician	Urology	SCI Outpatient Clinic Treatment of 3 patients during pregnancy; urologist since 6 years; worked in Switzerland and other countries in SCI clinics; treated SCI-related problems and diagnosed one pregnancy during examination for SCI-related problems.
15	Jonathan Steiner	Senior physician	Gynaecology	Private Practice / Visiting physician in SCI clinic Treatment of 1 patient during pregnancy; knowledge gained mainly through literature and online research.

ETHICAL APPROVAL AND CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE

According to the local ethical regulations this project does not fall under the remit of the Swiss Human Research Act [140]. The local ethic commission approved that this project does not collect health-related personal data, that means information concerning the health or disease of a specific or identifiable person, including genetic data (HRA, Art. 3, f – SR810.31). Oral informed consent was obtained and voice recorded before starting the interviews.

DATA ANALYSES

We resorted to analytical techniques developed within the framework of GT, acknowledging that different traditions of GT exist [141]. Our analysis was informed by the constructivist approach of Strauss and Corbin [142]. The Straussian approach to data analysis suggests a process of comparing concepts and their relationships. Moreover to pay attention to wider contextual factors that can influence a situation. Using GT analysis to data allows inductive category development as opposed to impose predefined categories on the data.

Accordingly, the interview transcripts were analysed using open and axial coding [137]. We focussed on scrutinising interview transcripts line by line to explore concepts that appeared in the data and writing first memos about conceptual and theoretical ideas that emerged during the course of the analysis. We repeatedly went through the interviews and merged open codes and memos into possible categories. The combination of open coding with increasingly focussed procedures contributed to the development of a deeper understanding of the content and meaning of the text [142]. The open coding was done independently by the first author (SB) and the research assistant. After open coding, coder checking occurred by engaging in an iterative process of refinement of categories between the two initial coders and co-authors (JP and TM).

During the process of axial coding, which was our second step, we used the 'paradigm model' of Strauss and Corbin [137]. We coded for similarities and differences in the data, which involved constantly comparing indicators and concepts, which in turn led to new concepts [142]. The goal during this process was to elaborate the central categories for the theory on the experiences of the professionals in caring for pregnant women with SCI and their different

expressions in the data. The main aim of this step was to identify the *central phenomenon* of the data. Our study participants had certain ways in which they dealt with the phenomenon, which we listed under the term *strategies*. The strategies then had certain *consequences*. The listed *contextual conditions* are coded (according to Strauss and Corbin's suggested practise) as belonging to the central phenomenon. Each contextual condition should represent the particular set of conditions that provide a framework in which the phenomenon under study takes place. Within the structural conditions are *actions*, which are referred to as the *intervening conditions* [142]. The axial coding was performed by the first author in regular meetings with the last author using a critical perspective with focus to the action and interaction strategies of the experts.

The study's *internal validity* [143] was enhanced by triangulation of different professional perspectives from the research team that consisted of a social researcher (SB) and paraplegic women with a special emphasis on women's views [68, 91, 133]; a research assistant with background in health sciences and policy, the second author (JP) with leading experience in the field of urology working in a SCI rehab clinic [68, 144]; and a senior researcher (last author, TM) experienced in qualitative and health services research [145, 146]. This procedure helped ensure that conclusions drawn from the authors were not based on a single perspective and helped to specify the resulting categories by an iterative reflection of the empirical data. Due to the small sample size and size variation in the groups, the results are mostly discussed as a whole, without addressing specific differences, similarities, or commonalities in between the groups.

We used MAXQDA10 for the open coding process and the visual software programme Mindjet 14 for developing and visualizing the categories and subcategories. Mindjet 14 allowed us to manage large amounts of data in a direct and uncomplicated way.

RESULTS

Coding data obtained from the 15 interviews provided a number of categories that could be arranged under a core topic Figure 5. The core category was derived from the service providers' experiences while caring for women with SCI during their pregnancies and births. The way the service providers treated

their patients was largely influenced by how they conceived their roles and their feelings of responsibility.

The treatment of women during this rare event presented a special challenge for the service providers. Our interpretation is that the service providers felt uncertain when treating these women. This uncertainty endangers an individual's ability to treat and function optimally, which is closely associated with the ability to control and predict situations. Service providers' experiences provide information about how efforts to regain certainty were initiated. The following elucidates the area of conflict among the treatment scenarios by means of different interconnected aspects resulting from the individual categories.

CAUSAL CONDITIONS

Every health professional mentioned the absence of a contact point for pregnant women with SCI. They were not able to name any individuals or institutions that offer explicit services or consultations for pregnant women with SCI. We assume that the rarity of the event is, due to its small incidence, also characterized by the absence of specialised providers.

'I think it is [the event] simply too rare. There is no one who really knows how it works best.' Jonathan Steiner, gynaecologist

The health professionals also highlighted further reasons that could lead to the phenomenon, such as progress in the field of medicine, increasing number of specialisations, and high expectations from pregnant paraplegic women vis-à-vis the healthcare system, resulting in these women having increased interactions with different healthcare professionals.

'...that (pregnant women with SCI) is (a) relatively rare (phenomenon), and I believe that knowledge isn't so abundant among urologists and gynaecologists that one can say that everybody can treat it.' Alexander Brand, urologist

Figure 5: Delivering care under uncertainty in pregnant women with SCI (Coding paradigm following Strauss and Corbin, 1996)

PHENOMENON

We identified *care delivery under uncertainty in a rare event* as the core category. The structural supply gaps described under the causal condition force service providers to provide treatment that is unfamiliar due to the complexity of care for pregnant women with SCI. The service provider must take many more factors into consideration than when treating an able-bodied woman. The attending physicians had neither the experience nor the competency to be able to comprehend all these factors and predict possible interactions, which creates a feeling of uncertainty. Everyone wanted to be able to precisely appraise what will happen during treatment. The interviewees expressed this by stating their uncertainty. However, not every participant spoke about his/her uncertainty or described this conflict. Based on the described patterns, we interpreted the service providers' behaviour as coping mechanisms in the face of uncertainty. This uncertainty was observed among individuals and can be attributed to others. We assume that this uncertainty characterizes the experience of all the professionals interviewed. The role of a decision maker is often assigned to service providers, thus they have no choice but to accept the challenge facing them. Decisions had to be made, however, not only on the basis of current knowledge but also on missing knowledge and uncertainty. Unfortunately, many service providers face missing knowledge and uncertainty when dealing with women with SCI, which created an undesired and unpleasant situation for both the pregnant women and their providers.

'One notices (it) a bit among midwives. I also noticed it among physicians, that enormous fear or maybe ignorance exists about caring for the women. I wish that it would be actually accepted as an open topic. That the women (in wheelchairs) would be greeted just as openly as women who are not in a wheelchair. Because they deserve exactly the same care as the others. One need not be afraid.'

Anna Weiss, midwife

In the following example, we describe a situation to illustrate the perceived uncertainty. A urologist explains to a pregnant woman with SCI how her gynaecologist could conduct a prenatal exam. We attribute the gynaecologist's refusal to take over treatment to his/her fear of causing possible harm to the woman or child due to insufficient knowledge.

'I can remember one (pregnant woman with SCI) quite well who asked me how a prenatal exam is carried out because the gynaecologists did not dare to conduct the gynaecological examination. She was tetraplegic, and they were afraid that they

would induce autonomic dysregulation if they performed a vaginal examination.’ Michael Brunner, urologist

CONTEXTUAL AND INTERVENING CONDITIONS

Health professionals

The willingness of service providers to treat pregnant women with SCI can be triggered, intensified, or weakened by different conditions and can influence service providers’ coping with uncertainty during treatment.

Differences in willingness to contribute to care delivery for pregnant women with SCI

From our point of view, as soon as one takes responsibility for other individuals and their concerns, the fear of mistakes or one’s own failure generally arise. Every health professional is exposed to this risk and must learn to deal with it. A health professional’s fear serves as an indicator of the degree to which s/he is consciously aware of the risks and how s/he deals with them professionally. This is related to not only the fear of a treatment mistake, but also fear of personal failure, which accompanies every medical action from the very beginning and leads to different degrees of willingness to deliver treatment, as our study participants have experienced in themselves or their colleagues.

‘...among gynaecologists, reservations apparently exist against treating such cases. An affected woman told me that she had difficulty finding a gynaecologist who said that he felt competent to treat someone sitting in a wheelchair and being pregnant.’ Michael Brunner, urologist

Differences in professional role perception and the accompanying willingness to take responsibility for treatments were observed among all participants. The interviewed gynaecologists saw their responsibility in the specialised and methodically appropriate treatment of gynaecological problems and their gynaecological services. Similar attitudes closely related to the tasks within their specialisation could also be identified among the interviewed midwives. They usually refer these women to specialists for spinal cord medicine for their SCI problems. Specialists for spinal cord medicine behaved differently. They were more concerned about the holistic well-being of the pregnant women and were aware of the urgency of their needs. We assumed that these differences in the service spectrums are anchored in the characteristics of the participants’

specialisations. Specialists like gynaecologists and midwives might consider themselves responsible for organ systems but not holistic spinal-gynaecological problem constellations. In contrast, those specialised in spinal cord medicine are trained in and confronted with interdisciplinary thinking.

'PMR professionals don't only treat urologic problems—I have also treated acute cases of paraplegia. I have seen patients with decubitus; I have also treated problems in internal medicine among paraplegics. I think that medical science is a broad field and urologists are urologists and gynaecologists are gynaecologists. Period.' Julia Peter, PMR professional

Another factor that influences taking over responsibility is familiarity with the topic. We witnessed a difference between participants who had never come across spinal cord medicine in their normal daily routine and those who had an experience of one kind or another with spinal cord medicine. There were individuals that clearly declined responsibility for spinal cord treatment, and others with long-term experience in caring for pregnant women with SCI who had amassed a lot of experience in such cases.

'...the PMR professionals told me where they saw the problem from their point of view, and I tried to translate that for myself. When the PMR professionals said, "spasticity or vegetative dystonia", I considered what that could mean for the pregnancy. I tried to observe the foetal development and the woman with SCI separately. I quickly noticed that the SCI actually had relatively little importance in the pregnancy and foetal development.' Matthias Gerber, gynaecologist

Occasionally, the suspicion was expressed that colleagues took over the complicated care of pregnant women with SCI for reasons of prestige.

'It is usually very interesting for the gynaecologists to care for such a woman, and they want to keep the woman. Self-interest also plays a role.' Anna Weiss, midwife

However, participants also expressed assumptions that colleagues would not trust themselves to take over such care. There were even signs of refusal to accept these complex tasks.

'I believe they are afraid of complications. Of complications with autonomic hyperreflexia or, for example, that complications would arise with the paraplegia, that there would somehow be a rupture. I think it is easy: if someone has no knowledge about it, one also is afraid. I can, of course, understand that.' Anna Weiss, midwife

'Anaesthesiologists know what to do during a caesarean section. In contrast, SCI with lumbar anaesthesia plus no sensitivity, I think that is just too precarious for them.' Franziska Schneider, midwife

Differences in the willingness to cooperate interdisciplinary

Inexperience in treatment modalities or possible undesired treatment results appear everywhere in healthcare, more so when the service provider is confronted with situations in which crucial decisions must be made. The important aspect is how individuals react and their willingness to make corrections. A possible component that became evident in the interviews is that no systematic contact was sought with colleagues or other specialists during pregnancy.

'No. I don't speak to the gynaecologists. There is no exchange. If any, then with the doctors (PMR professionals) here at the centre.'
Jasmin Rieger, peer counsellor

'That was more one way, or it was at least not interdisciplinary. It wasn't that a gynaecologist called me and said, "I have a patient here", or that I spoke with the gynaecologist afterwards. The three patients whom I remember just now took things into their own hands—the communication. They got advice from me and then said, "Good, now I know, that's enough." The gynaecologist never called me about these patients, and I didn't call the gynaecologist.' Michael Brunner, urologist

Cooperation and team effort were different during the phase of a forthcoming birth. In this case, we observed signs of cooperation, initiated especially by the attending specialist. The person in charge, usually the gynaecologist, called for team meetings with the anaesthesiologist, midwife, and nurse and informed his/her team of the impending birth.

'An epidural anaesthesia does not present a problem for the anaesthetist, and the woman's handicap is also not a problem for the midwife. Of course we discussed it.' Matthias Gerber, gynaecologist

'Completely normal; there was a midwife during the birth, and as I said, caesarean section. We had arranged a discussion with the anaesthetist in advance. When there is a special existing disease, we don't do that only a day before the planned caesarean section, but we plan things a little better in advance.' Martin Roggo, gynaecologist

Differences in the willingness to integrate health competencies of women with SCI in the care process

We observed that all participants had similar perceptions on how to handle medical health problems by participating in decision making. The interviewees recognized a high level of health literacy in the women with SCI. They described them as active and well-educated in health matters and as someone who searched for relevant information online or obtained information from their social surroundings. The interviewees also said that the pregnant women with SCI had a thorough knowledge of paraplegia, but insufficient knowledge about gynaecological and postnatal topics. The service providers with little knowledge about SCI often relied on the knowledge and arguments of the women with SCI and included them in the treatment processes and decisions.

'What occurred to me (is that) women who have given birth and sit in a wheelchair, they are like a mobile library. They know so much, one can really suck up their knowledge. I consider them to be the best sources of information.' Anna Weiss, midwife

Standards and scientific evidence

We consider that the guidelines produced by scientific specialist societies are of decisive importance for the treatments delivered by the service provider. The practice derives relevance from the description of medical standards. This knowledge is indispensable to enable service providers to avoid substantial treatment errors. They are practice-oriented aids for decisions concerning the course of treatment in the presence of special health problems. All study participants complained in general about the lack of guidelines, little existing scientific literature, and the lack of a central database.

'No, there is no knowledge and very little literature available. So, if you care for a woman with SCI, then you need to inform yourself.' Anna Weiss, midwife

'...urologists who are allowed to participate in the care of such patients do that with a good conscience—or at least I hope so. But nobody makes it transparent. There are, however, certain cooperation's—the beginning of an exchange about different things. But there is no compilation of knowledge to provide a better basis for decision making.' Michael Brunner, urologist

It is usually accepted that the treatment provided by professionals is a mixture of their expertise, intuition, and the art of healing. The modern concept of evidence-based medicine demands that decisions have to be made whenever

possible on the basis of empirically proven effectiveness. We experienced that the lack of easy-to-use tools forces professionals to rely on their specialist knowledge, which only partially covers the demands of treating spinal-gynaecological conditions. This inadequate knowledge certainly contributes directly to professionals' uncertainty and can influence their willingness to provide medical care.

'Which therapies exist? What is allowed, and what is not? Where do we have experience, and where do we have none? I believe we simply have little experience. There are few statistically confirmed data on what is good and what is not good. We have to honestly admit that.'
Alexander Brand, urologist

Healthcare organizations

It is known that access to appropriate medical care helps women maintain or improve their health. The study participants reported on the structural and architectural barriers fulfilling the needs of women with SCI.

Although most hospitals in Switzerland are equipped for persons with disabilities, we identified signs that the furnishings and equipment inside are not optimal for medical examinations of women with SCI. The interviewees initially had the impression that the practice or hospital would be entirely accessible and would meet the needs of disabled women. Only after specific requests with concrete examples did health professionals reflect on possible barriers. For example, there are no examination tables with adjustable heights, no scales, and the examination rooms are excessively narrow. In addition, the toilets are located on a different floor.

'Yes, that's right, we don't have scales.' Martin Roggo, gynaecologist
'Speaking of toilets – we do have a special toilet for people with disabilities. It isn't on the same floor, but it is on a floor below.'
Matthias Gerber, gynaecologist

Over and above the lack of documented knowledge, we found indications that the architecture of healthcare settings do not cater to spinal-gynaecological services in Switzerland. For example, rehabilitation centres can care for women with SCI during their pregnancy. However, they are not equipped for gynaecological treatments such as regular examinations during pregnancy.

'There isn't anyone with exact knowledge about these things. Everyone knows a little bit. It is a very, very specialised topic. But there is no competent person who has knowledge of every aspect.'

'We don't have gynaecological equipment here, that's right. But even if we had it, a specialist from gynaecology would have to do it.'
Nicole Müller, PMR professional

'There is good access, one can use the examination rooms well, but then a gynaecologist is required who ideally would, for example, conduct preventive examinations. We don't have that here, and not everyone can bring her own gynaecologist here. When a pregnant woman comes here and I want to do a urologic examination, it is absolutely no problem. But if I am not sure if there is also a gynaecologic problem, I cannot find that out here. Then I send her back to her treating gynaecologist, but I do not know and cannot influence how access is there, whether barriers exist to reaching the service. Sure, it's not a problem here, but there is no gynaecologist here.' Michael Brunner, urologist

In summary, access to medical care cannot be regarded as patient-specific in this group of patients. The inadequate medical services offered can influence the choice of physician and add to the uncertainty faced during the provision of care.

STRATEGY

Strategies applied to cope with uncertainty

We observed different mechanisms for coping with uncertainty. The different approaches, e.g. *'...in the worst case, I simply try to build a good working relationship with the gynaecologists'* Georg Fischer, PMR professional, and *'...close medical supervision...'* Martin Roggo, gynaecologist, clearly indicate the different ways in which the participants deal with uncertainty. These strategies can be categorized into the following types: (i) *protective concerned attitude*, exhibiting great confidence in one's own abilities usually based on long-term experience in the chosen specialty; (ii) *'no big deal' attitude*, with a selective provision of information and the tendency to only react when problems arise; and (iii) *precautionary attitude*, which is characterized by many examinations.

Protective concerned attitude

A protective concerned approach to cope with uncertainty in the provision of care corresponds with medical care to protect the woman. The service provider

radiates great reliability. This occurs without losing sight of optimal specialist care and a certain degree of quality of care by all involved parties. The characteristics of service providers from this category are focussed less on maintaining formal, logical treatment standards, but more on the ability to recognize patterns. The practitioners apply flexible treatment approaches based on clinical experiences.

'In principle, I would reduce antibiotic treatment as much as possible. Since the problem is common, and we see that even now, regardless of pregnancy, many patients with bacteriuria are treated, despite it being unnecessary. It is simply done; there are bacteria in the urine, and they are treated with an antibiotic. In a pregnant woman, especially if she is asymptomatic and shows no signs of a really complicated ascending infection, I would not give a long-term prophylaxis during the pregnancy.' Alexander Brandt, urologist

We observed this kind of coping with uncertainty by service providers had long-term clinical experiences combined with leading positions.

'You know, in the worst case I simply try to build up a good working relationship with the gynaecologists. If the woman feels insecure, we have to discuss it. If possible, all three of us; otherwise only with the gynaecologists. We usually come up with a good solution, and things turn out well.' I am always reassured when I have spoken to him (the gynaecologist) and when I see that he understands the problems or the possible problems.' Georg Fischer, PMR professional

With a protective concerned attitude, the aspect of high specialist proficiency comes to the fore accompanied by a curiosity to learn more about the problem. Most health professionals with this attitude endeavoured to find possible solutions for therapeutic interventions.

'What I have learned and my experience, in principle, I owe it to the patients. From the very beginning, my patients have told me things; I tried to remember and apply this to the next patients. All the tips and tricks I have learned have all been from the patients.' Georg Fischer, PMR professional

'In all the package inserts of drugs to treat bladder spasticity, it says that they are contraindicated in pregnancy. If you inform yourself more thoroughly and read up, there are apparently certain periods during pregnancy when this medication caused something in animal experiments. If you compare the doses that were given to the animals to what is administered to humans, the animals got higher doses, i.e. it says apodictically that one must not give it, but if you

look at what that's based on and take the trouble to do that for every single medicine, you will find out that that it is not apodictically true. But these data are very, very difficult to obtain; there is hardly any transparency, e.g. from the manufacturers. I really took the effort until I got any data at all from the different manufacturers. And then you have to see to what degree these data from animal experiments can be transferred to humans. There is little cooperation because there is also little interest on the part of the pharmaceutical companies that produce the medication.'
Michael Brunner, urologist

'No big deal' attitude

The 'no big deal' attitude is practiced by service providers who provide services only for pregnant women. Pregnant women with SCI are not considered as special cases by these service providers, and they treat them like every other pregnant woman. Even if each pregnant woman with SCI is an individual case and this can be firmly anchored in the service provider's memory, it generally becomes blurred in the multitude of cases. As new patients are always waiting to be seen, the attending physician rarely spends more time than necessary on individual cases. He intervenes with help and support only if the woman explicitly expresses the need or if the medical situation calls for it. The help rendered is limited to the physician's specialty and involves hardly any support for SCI comorbidities in the sense of directly taking over responsibility for all health-related problems. Another aspect of the 'no big deal' attitude is the selective information behaviour of the service provider.

'...I consider the pregnancy as such to be unproblematic. She is just a patient like any other.' Jonathan Steiner, gynaecologist

Interviewer: 'Did she have several, did she have more frequent ultrasounds?'

Interviewee: 'No, absolutely not.'

Interviewer: 'You may have been confronted with diverse secondary complications, like urologic problems and problems with bowel management. How did you solve these problems? Did she simply inform you of them, or did she consult someone else, or how did you handle the situation?'

Interviewee: 'It was never actually brought up.' Jonathan Steiner, gynaecologist

'I mention it when I notice that it presents a problem for the woman. I do not do it on principle, in one fell swoop, like with you now, that you hear everything at once.' Elisabeth Frey, gynaecologist

'One need not necessarily communicate the problems to the patient, perhaps not to frighten her, but you have to have it in the back of your head and can then gradually integrate it into the process if need be.' Jonathan Steiner, gynaecologist

Precautionary attitude

Service providers take over responsibility as a form of precautionary action, especially when expectations from them are perceived as exceptionally high. Our investigation revealed that those service providers with few such cases are overburdened with the specialist-oriented support. They attempt to cover the medical aspects of both the gynaecological and paraplegic fields. As a result, the service provider often has to master highly complex issues and must decide accordingly under conditions of high uncertainty. Self-proclaimed expertise and the resulting responsibility obligate one to practice conscientiously. The aspects of a precautionary attitude were more examinations and a systematic administration of preventive medication. This kind of behaviour can be understood as an avoidance manoeuvre and a sign of helplessness in dealing with the treatment situation. The service provider tends to make an increased number of diagnoses to be sure to cover all eventualities. We observed this attitude in gynaecologists as well as PMR professionals.

'You are already relatively restrictive in normal pregnancies, or you will treat every pregnant woman with even the slightest sign of a urinary tract infection. This is truer for women with SCI. Then you are actually even stricter.' Nicole Müller, PMR professional

'We naturally see these patients at shorter intervals, by shorter I mean we perform a control check-up every 3-4 weeks to have the parameters better under control.' Martin Schüssler, gynaecologist

CONSEQUENCES

We have argued above that management in this particular situation can be understood as attempts to restore security. As a consequence, the professionals try to withstand the uncertainty or hand it over. Sometimes role allocation and responsibility were unclear during the treatment process, and the service provider saw him/herself as only a part of this process. This can be recognized in the call for interdisciplinary collaboration.

Withstanding or handing over uncertainty

The study participants tried to confront their lack of knowledge by withstanding the situation, acquiring further knowledge, or handing over responsibility and tried to re-establish certainty. Some attempted to reduce the feeling of uncertainty by referring the pregnant woman with SCI to a different institution or by taking a lot of precautions. Others withstood the uncertainty and tried to better protect themselves by maintaining collaborations or networking with other professionals.

'What else can you do? So that I don't just stand there like a fool. You thought over what you would do for a bladder infection. Can you do something preventive? Can you do something against obstipation? Can you do something to reduce the risk of thrombosis? And so on.' Matthias Gerber, gynaecologist

'For patients who have questions concerning bladder-sedating medication, there is no reliable answer because all these medicaments carry a theoretical risk, which must be prevented during pregnancy. I always gave a conscientious answer according to my best knowledge after consulting with other urologists. That satisfied the patients, and nothing happened to the children. That's the best we can say.' Alexander Brandt, urologist

The difficulties and challenges that the professionals have to overcome in addition to all other expectations of medical service can be considered as burdens. An initial open and positive attitude toward the treatment of a pregnant woman with SCI could change during treatment. A midwife, after reflecting, expressed the wish to hand over responsibility for pregnant women with SCI.

'...just someone who can share his experience or even just cares for the women from beginning until the end. Without upcoming doubts or uncertainty. Or, as I said, somebody who has the knowledge and can pass it on or spread the knowledge. That would be great!' Anna White, midwife

Actor in a fragmented care process

A further consequence was the individual interaction with other professionals providing specialist treatment. Professionals especially from the field of spinal cord medicine were left in the dark with respect to how their treatment had

affected the pregnancy and the child. Sometimes, they were also confronted with the women's frustration resulting from being expected to make the decision concerning a medical problem by themselves. Professionals responsible for specialist treatment found themselves in an area of conflict among fragmented treatments, pregnant women requiring information, and their uncertain role in the treatment process.

The gynaecologist will tell her something about pregnancy. We will tell her something urologic and maybe something about possible complications. But we do not sit down together, and then she's there and asks herself, 'What should I do now?' The gynaecologist said everything is easy going just like anybody else, although maybe he has only seen one or two such women in his life. In principle we say that, as far as we know, the women we have seen are fine, but there are these and these risks.' Alexander Brand, urologist

Call for interdisciplinary collaboration

The increasing number of specialisations in our healthcare system has made a holistic view of the patients more demanding. What is needed is, therefore, an interdisciplinary collaboration by health professionals of all specialisations. The topic of interdisciplinary collaboration with respect to the supervision of pregnant women with SCI was broached in this context. We interpret the desire, above all among PMR professionals, for more interdisciplinary collaboration, even education from competency centres, as a result of the lack of institutionalized cooperation up until now. Interdisciplinary collaboration would liberate service providers from having to make decisions alone.

Pregnancy and paraplegia, that's not an everyday situation. Not every gynaecologist can deal with it, maybe not even every urologist. It is not very common even in specialised centres for SCI. I believe, perhaps an idea would be if one simply said, 'OK, let's combine them in a certain centre'....because I certainly lack some gynaecological aspects, I have to admit it. I know I cannot administrate that drug, I should not prescribe it. We should simply collaborate together, also for infections. The gynaecologist may use a dipstick and say, 'Good, it's positive; we have to treat her. I must give her a prophylaxis.' We see that differently from a urologic point of view. I believe it would make sense to say, 'OK, we put them all together in a centre and generate experience in a centre for that kind of thing.'" Alexander Brand, urologist

'I also believe that gynaecologists should know that they are dealing with special cases and that they also (should) enter into collaboration with rehabilitation centres. I do not think that someone in an outpatient clinic, a general practitioner, can do that. I do not think so. But, as I said, we are not gynaecologists, i.e., patients also need a gynaecologist. There simply must be cooperation, also after pregnancy.' Julia Peter, PMR professional

DISCUSSION

This study presents insights into the experiences of health professionals in caring for women with SCI during pregnancy and childbirth. The professionals reflected on a number of issues that affected their care delivery and interactions with pregnant women with SCI as well as with colleagues and allied health professionals.

The emergent core category was *delivering care under uncertainty in a rare event* (Fig. 1). The *rarity of the event* is characterized by the absence of specialised providers, few scientific publications, and a lack of specific sources of information and appropriate standards. Another emergent term in our core category was *uncertainty*. Uncertainty has been researched in various disciplines, including sociology [147, 148], psychology [149, 150], health services research [151], and patient counselling [152], and it provides several conceptual meanings that are in many cases not that different [153-155]. We share the view of Babrow [156], who states that uncertainty exists when details of situations are ambiguous, complex, unpredictable, or very probabilistic; when information is unavailable or inconsistent; and when people feel insecure in their own state of knowledge or the state of knowledge in general. Uncertainty in healthcare is experienced by not only clinicians but also patients [153, 157].

In people with SCI, subjective symptoms can be attributed to numerous health problems [52]. The trajectory of the pregnancy varies substantially among women [91], and as the study results indicate, some treatments can be considered experimental. Healthcare providers and patients both encounter complexity and ambiguity in decisions about diagnoses and treatments, which later on may be proved false. The aetiology of health states comprises various

possible biopsychosocial factors; symptoms may be attributed to different paraplegic comorbidities or unknown causes, and healthcare providers may offer different diagnoses when assessing the same symptom pattern. The complexity endangers the healthcare professionals' ability to treat and function optimally, which is closely associated with the ability to control and predict care situations.

The three strategies identified in this study, i) protective concerned attitude; ii) no big deal attitude; and iii) precautionary attitude, are seen as different ways in which health professionals manage the complex care situation. Identifying strategies [158] offers a possible explanation for how health professionals handle uncertainty and complexity. It provides a contextual framework from which to view clinical decision making. Although health professionals may not be able to come up with a clear-cut diagnosis, they could deal with patients' concerns by talking about the probable diagnoses or by alleviating fears about treatments and restoring a certain level of security. The identified strategies can also reveal approaches and methods for problem solving.

The contextual conditions identified in this study (fig. 1) are not only directly related to the core phenomenon. They may have also implicitly influenced the set of attitudinal responses of health professionals to the resulting phenomenon. In our view, the uncertainty of health professionals stems from different reasons and is related to the structural and architectural difficulties in accessing medical care, the lack of standards, and poor scientific literature as well as the behaviours of individual health professionals. Similar contextual findings have been observed and discussed as barriers in earlier research, e.g. inaccessible healthcare provider offices in general for mobility-impaired people and unfamiliarity of specific providers with fertility, pregnancy, and SCI [159, 160]. Equitable healthcare cannot be guaranteed under these conditions [161].

Some recommendations for the treatment or monitoring of women with SCI during pregnancy and childbirth are available in English-speaking regions [115, 162-164]. The German medical association for spinal cord injury (Deutsche Medizinische Gesellschaft für Paraplegie) is currently working on recommendations in German. Unfortunately, thus far, none of the available information seems to have reached healthcare professionals.

This has serious implications on care delivery. Possible paraplegic comorbidities that might arise during a pregnancy with SCI remain unknown to

professionals. Preventive measures are not applied routinely on the patient. Additionally, recommended preventive measures and diagnostic and laboratory tests may not be carried out. A previous study demonstrates that 10 of 17 women were hospitalized during the course of their pregnancies [133]. The high number of hospitalizations indicates possible unfavourable decisions due to insufficient knowledge. These findings underline the importance of clinical research and the need for favourable 'daily' clinical training of health professionals on as many cases as possible in order to ensure optimal health for the mother and child.

The lack of specific experts and care programs for women with SCI during pregnancy and childbirth pose a serious question for health professionals: to what extent should they want to take over responsibility. Care delivery took place in two diverse medical specialties with different treatment philosophies, and the interviewees differed in their views on who should take the overall lead. On one side, we had gynaecologists and obstetricians specialised on an organ system or event. On the other side are professionals from the field of rehabilitation who are trained in delivering care for multiple organ systems and even psychosocial care. The different professional understandings affected the role and responsibility of how health professionals see their position in the care process for pregnant women with SCI.

The results of this study indicate a need to integrate multiple professional perspectives in the care process in order to optimize care and treatment to people where fragmentations in care had led to unfavourable care experiences and outcomes [91].

It became apparent that we face a structural problem. Health professionals support the idea of '*centralized*' care, whereas women with SCI favoured receiving care in their local environment as identified in a previous study. Pregnant women with SCI did not prefer travelling to a specific centre. Moreover, they did not like the idea of receiving care in a rehabilitation setting for their pregnancy concerns. On the other hand, the study participants mainly from the rehabilitation settings felt like a puzzle piece in the care process. One solution is to create a best practices model of how healthcare for women with SCI during pregnancy and childbirth could be performed at a top level and to enter in a stakeholder dialogue [165] with all groups. A recent study demonstrated that the effectiveness of integrated care projects is improved when all stakeholders perceive a high degree of integration. This emphasizes

the need to develop a multilayer commitment when leading integrated care efforts [166]. In the meantime, virtual places such as SCI parenting.com from the Spinalis Group in Sweden [128] or the guide for pregnancy with SCI of the Spinal Cord Injury Perinatal Interest Group (Rick Hansen Institute) from Canada [167] could serve as a case in point for the German-speaking region.

Another option is creating a clinical quality management system [168] that provides a framework for defining and delivering quality outcomes, managing risks, and continual improvement. The system should be set up as a learning system to define parameters that could be important for creating a database for pregnancy outcomes.

STUDY LIMITATIONS

The qualitative methodology allowed us to gather in-depth views on how health professionals experienced care delivery for women with SCI during pregnancy and childbirth. We decided to conduct individual interviews with the experts instead of focus groups or written interviews assuming that besides time constraints, the theme may not be that important to health professionals due to the limited overlap with their specialty. We aimed to increase the chances of participation by providing participants with the choice of an oral or telephone interview and allowing them to choose the location of the interview.

During expert recruitment, we had to consider the busy time schedule of the participating experts. Therefore, the interviews were limited in scope of potential for openness, possibly affecting the quality of information [169]. Face-to-face interviews would have been preferable in all cases, allowing for a better rapport and increased sensitivity to the more subtle issues at stake. Since interviews were conducted by well-trained researchers, we are confident of having gathered data on sensitive issues as well. The first author is a paraplegic woman who is familiar with SCI problems; enabling her to be sensitive both to her research perspective and to the situation of women with SCI. The research assistant learned continuously by assisting the initial interviews and shaped own interviews with her special interest for healthcare services use. Each interview style has advantages and disadvantages, and the differences eventually enriched the picture of health professionals' experiences. The assistants' lack of experience with SCI conditions sometimes encouraged the interviewees to explain in further detail. Additionally, the first author

challenged health professionals by using concrete examples from women with SCI and encouraged them to speak up openly about their own experiences.

In qualitative research, the question of the extent to which analyses are affected by the researchers' own values and objectives and its effect on the research project always arises [170]. We aimed to reduce the influence of single researchers' views by including different perspectives. The analysis was based on continuous discussions between the authors and research assistant throughout the process in order to increase the scrutiny and trustworthiness of the analysis. Moreover, the credibility of the results was enhanced by thoroughly reading and analysing the data during open and axial coding separately by two researchers before comparing and confirming the categories.

Since the sampling strategy was based on a previous study in which women named their treating health professionals, certain groups of importance in other healthcare systems, such as family doctors and neurologists, may not appear. This deliberate choice of focussing only on the known groups treating pregnant women with SCI may mean that certain perspectives were lost. This might have led to a restriction of possible experience from the professional side, albeit representing the current care situation of the women with SCI involved.

The small sample size does not allow for substantive comparisons between professional groups. Therefore, we primarily restricted our interpretation the group of professionals as a whole. During the analysis process, we had indications that health professionals' behaviour was primarily influenced by their experience and perceived role and not especially by their specialty. Therefore, we highlighted these aspects in the results.

Although the results refer primarily to the healthcare situation of pregnant women with SCI in Switzerland, the conceptual design of the core category allows a transfer to other special situations, such as multiple sclerosis and spina bifida, which are distinguished by a rare event and medical uncertainty.

CONCLUSIONS

These findings highlight the diversity of perspectives among different health professionals regarding the approach to care and service delivery for pregnant women with SCI. There is a need for specific services, more information, guidance, and guidelines for health professionals caring for woman with SCI

during pregnancy and childbirth. By drawing upon the study results and discussing possible solutions, we tried to provide realistic and feasible solutions, bearing in mind that the presented solutions may also be valid for a wider field that includes different disabilities as mentioned above. A centre of excellence not primarily for care, but for reference, which collects and evaluates clinical experiences with pregnant women with SCI may be a valuable aid for health professionals involved in the medical care of these patients. Alternatively, contradicting the wish of women, an interdisciplinary centre offering specialised care could be worthwhile solution.

While it is important to better comprehend the complex and multidimensional nature of the rare event, it is also important to create integrated care designs in terms of promoting coordination and continuity of care and equity of access. We strongly recommend further prospective research on the development of integrated care concepts and support research with clinical impact, i.e. clinical studies on the subject to provide a broader evidence base for decision making and, ultimately, for reducing uncertainty for all stakeholders in this rare event.

GENERAL DISCUSSION

The three individual articles presented in this thesis examined the maternity care of women with SCIs during pregnancy and childbirth using data on the experiences of mothers with SCIs and the views of their health practitioners. The *first study* is a descriptive study showing that, as suggested by international research [43, 69, 171], urological problems are the most frequent complications during pregnancy. Contrary to international research [43, 69], however, the results did not reveal a high prevalence of pressure sores, thrombosis or autonomic dysreflexia (AD) events. Pregnant women with SCIs did not seek medical advice for every health condition (e.g. bowel problems or thrombosis prevention). The findings showed a tendency towards caesarean section in women with SCIs of nearly 70% and a rather high number, 10 out of 17, of pre-term hospitalisations.

Using the same sample, the *second study* ascertained that mothers with SCIs have specific service needs during pregnancy and childbirth. The six identified perceived service needs involved: a) information about being pregnant with an SCI; b) specific health practitioners' expertise; c) medical treatment; d) access to and availability of care facilities; e) specific supplies and equipment; and f) improved care integration. To address gynaecological concerns, participants visited practitioners in their home areas. Some contacted SCI centres for additional information relating to being pregnant with an SCI and were rather dissatisfied with the counselling, which they felt provided poor information. However, the women were satisfied with the urological counselling they received at outpatient clinics.

The *third study* used a grounded theory approach to analyse the experiences of health practitioners in delivering care to pregnant women with SCIs. These experiences were described as forced reactions to decision making under conditions of uncertainty. The three strategies identified were a protective concerned attitude, a 'no-big-deal' attitude, and a precautionary attitude. These attitudes were influenced by the health care system and existing policies and were characterised by health practitioners' personal behaviours.

Pregnant women with SCI present unique clinical challenges

Given the elevated risk for medical complications during pregnancy and childbirth due to SCIs [64, 72], the medical study in this doctoral thesis emphasises that many women with SCIs experienced complications. The most

frequently encountered SCI-related comorbidities during pregnancy are bladder and bowel problems, as reported elsewhere [68, 69, 130]. Contrary to other research [135, 172] occurrences of skin breakdown and thrombosis did not occur. Applying preventive health behaviour measures, such as resting more, elevating the legs and using compression stockings, reduced or eliminated complications. These precautionary measures could be attributed to the fact that almost all women have received good information on precautionary measures during pre-rehabilitation. While some diseases could be prevented, the medical study in this doctoral thesis revealed more severe complications (i.e. kidney infections, falls, elevated blood pressure and pregnancy intoxication) leading to prehospitalisation. The increased number of such events might be due to insufficient clinical knowledge about pregnancy with a SCI [106, 107]. However, additional research is needed to investigate this.

To optimise maternity care in Switzerland, it is necessary to have access to basic epidemiological indicators and high-quality data about health complications, which is particularly helpful for pregnancy counselling and the care and anticipation of potential complications in these complex pregnancies. Efforts are underway to prospectively collect such information via the next SwiSCI community survey, Pathway 2 [81].

Perinatal care experiences are not satisfactory for all women

The study of mothers with SCIs in this doctoral thesis shows that despite their having the same rights to access maternity care services as able-bodied women [113, 173], equal access is not yet the norm [174], and many challenges must be overcome before this can happen. It seems the Swiss health system is not adequately prepared to handle mothers with SCIs. In Switzerland, organisational components relating to access and structure seem to be factors impeding adequate maternity care for women with SCIs. As mentioned in the literature reviewed [18, 79, 84], the degree of access to medical care for pregnant women with SCIs is hampered by several architectonic barriers and reduced possibilities for service selection. The structures through which health care is provided lack guidelines and information specific to caring for women with SCIs and/or specific to maternity care settings, and health care equipment and materials are often absent or inadequate for effective as proposed as necessary in the literature [43, 79, 174].

Study results of this thesis also revealed a high demand for specialised antenatal services that are more client centred. The fragmentations in receiving care puts women in an uncomfortable situation. They feel alone and responsible for treatment decisions. One approach to tackle this issue is to emphasise on factors (*women's health literacy, mobility restriction, social embedding*) [175, 176] with a substantial impact in women's health during the perinatal period.

Health practitioner's need more support to respond adequately to women's health needs

The practitioner study in this doctoral thesis describes the challenges of health practitioners in delivering care to pregnant women with SCIs. The findings reveal disagreements between involved parties in the understanding of care. With gynaecologists and obstetricians specialising in the reproductive system on one side and rehabilitation physicians trained in treating multiple organ systems on the other, the different professional understandings of the body affect health practitioners' views regarding their roles and responsibilities in caring for pregnant women with SCIs. This in turn, leads to an even greater fragmentation in health care. A widespread consensus is that fragmented care leads to increased costs and higher rates of preventable hospitalisation [177]. The elevated number (10/17) of prenatal hospitalisations observed in the medical study in this doctoral thesis could be a result of the fragmented care received. However, this is a speculative assumption based on a small sample and requires further investigation.

Because different health practitioners in different settings are involved in the care process at different time points, the findings of this doctoral thesis underline the need for developing care plans for treating pregnant women with SCIs [47]. However, this suggestion needs a consensus dialogue between all stakeholders to define clear responsibilities and roles in caring for pregnant women with SCIs [177, 178]. Given the stakeholder power of policymakers and clinical directors [165], it may be possible to reduce costs and improve quality for maternity care.

In summary, a clear finding of this doctoral thesis is the unique clinical challenges when caring for pregnant women with SCIs. It seems there were no specialised pregnancy counselling services, and the lack of specific

comprehensive knowledge, cooperation and regulations caused confusion and even tension between the patients and health practitioners.

STRENGTHS AND LIMITATIONS OF THE THESIS

The empirical studies discussed in this doctoral thesis have some strengths and limitations. A main strength of this thesis is that it gives a voice to the experts, that is, both the mothers with SCIs and the practitioners who care for them during pregnancy and birth. Integrating the women's and health practitioners' views [179, 180] supports their right to be heard on one hand and fosters the credibility of the research on the other [123, 143, 181]. The methodological choices to include quantitative and qualitative aspects resulted in deeper insight and more detailed information to explain the complexity of maternity care for women with SCIs. In qualitative research, the question of how the analysis is affected by the researchers' views and values always arises. Trustworthiness in the mothers with SCIs and in the practitioners study was ensured by always including two or more researchers with different backgrounds in the analysis process [170].

There exists no official register of women with SCIs who give birth in Switzerland. This influenced the study sampling for the medical study and mothers with SCI study and may have led to selection bias. This is why I had to rely on the data of the SwiSCI Cohort study and recruit participants directly from the SCI community. This allowed me to recruit all over Switzerland but did not support sample representativeness or the generalisability of results [50, 182]. Only German- and French-speaking women were included; Italian-speaking women were excluded. Even though the proportion of Italian speakers is small in Switzerland, this restriction influenced the representativeness of the study sample and thereby the degree to which the study results can be generalised to the whole population of women with SCIs in Switzerland. The reason for including only German- and French-speaking women was that the researchers involved in the analysis only spoke these two languages.

Another important methodological issue is that the reported data might be affected by recall bias. Recall bias refers to the phenomenon that over time, certain things tend to become more difficult to remember [183]. The data had to rely on the openness and memories of mothers and practitioners, and the

data may not have accurately presented all the medical complications or interventions experienced. It might be difficult for women to remember which medical complication occurred fifteen years after giving birth. The same concerns are valid for the questionnaire of the medical study discussed in this doctoral thesis. Because data was self-reported, some information may be imprecise or might have been forgotten.

POLICY AND CLINICAL RECOMMENDATIONS

Raising Awareness

It is important for clinicians in all medical fields to know that women with SCIs can get pregnant and become mothers and that they need special care. However, past research has shown that some clinicians do not fully understand the extent of complications, the possible related risk for negative health outcomes and show negative attitudes [184]. In their daily practice, a pregnant woman with an SCI may just be one case and, perhaps understandably, not their priority. However, every individual has the right to the best care possible, and in my view, clinical attention and awareness should improve. The important question is: how can we attract clinical attention for this patient group? Is this patient group just too time-consuming, or are clinicians perhaps overwhelmed by such cases? If they are overwhelmed, what can be done to help reduce their fears/anxiety? Should a specialty centre take over the care of this patient group? Or would it be better to train clinicians to care for this patient group? I do not yet have the answers; however, I want to raise clinicians' awareness of this patient group and their special needs by presenting the results of this doctoral thesis to various associations (i.e. gynaecological and midwifery associations) and at various events (i.e. gynaecological and spinal cord medicine) in Switzerland.

Guidelines for Health Care Provision during Maternity

One frequent critique in the scientific literature is that standard practices for providing care to mothers with SCIs and their babies are not based on scientific evidence concerning the most beneficial practices [174, 175]. There are currently efforts to develop guidelines for the care of women with SCIs during pregnancy and childbirth in Germany. The results of this doctoral thesis were incorporated in the development of the German Medical Society for Spinal Cord (DMGP) and German Society for Gynaecology and Obstetrics (DGGG) guidelines for health care provision during the pregnancy, birth and postpartum period of women with SCIs [185]. More concrete themes and content regarding the necessity and benefits of interprofessional and interdisciplinary collaboration of practitioners when caring for pregnant women with SCIs were included. A further theme relates to the advantages of including the health literacy of future mothers with SCIs in treatment plans, particularly their knowledge of body functions.

Spinal Cord Injury Training for Health Practitioners

Next to awareness, the various unmet needs of pregnant women with SCIs that were identified in this doctoral thesis suggest some concrete ideas for training for health practitioners in SCI. Health practitioners' lack of training and education relating to maternity care for women with SCIs prevents women from receiving optimal care [186]. Health practitioners feel that education and training in disabilities could reduce health practitioners' biases regarding the provision of care to women with disabilities. This idea is supported by evidence relating to the general and specialty care of people with different disabilities [187, 188]. One way to address this problem is to introduce disability training in medical education, as suggested in other medical professions [189, 190].

Specific Pregnancy Counselling Services

I must admit that it surprised me that pregnancy counselling still plays a relatively minor role in specialised SCI settings Switzerland. This doctoral thesis identified no or restricted pregnancy counselling service in most rehabilitation centres and outpatient clinics. To receive good pregnancy

counselling, I recommend that women with SCIs consult a physical and rehabilitation medicine professional (PMR) with extensive knowledge of gynaecology and urology. During consultations, the PMR can talk about the injury and explain what it means for the pregnancy, labour and delivery. Such counselling includes spinal cord and urological check-ups and review of medication. The PMR can also help to find a local gynaecologist or other medical specialists the women may need during pregnancy. This counselling service plays an important part in identifying pregnant women at risk for SCI complications and in providing information to women with SCIs, their partners and other clinicians about how to deal with the SCI and any potential problems. The usefulness of counselling services for women who are or plan to become pregnant has been shown elsewhere [174, 175].

FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTION

Data Needs for the Future

This doctoral thesis indicates that the available data about pregnancy in women with SCIs and specific SCI comorbidities is insufficient. However, further cause-effect data would be beneficial before elaborating care plans for pregnant women. For instance, further research, including basic epidemiological indicators and information about obstetrical issues (i.e. preterm delivery, birth indicators), is needed to establish comprehensive care plans for pregnancy with an SCI. Retrospective data collection is difficult in Switzerland because women are treated in different settings. A suitable solution is to use data from the upcoming SwiSCI Pathway 2 [81] survey that will collect new information, including birth data of children of people with SCIs.

A Perinatal Health Framework for Women with a Disability

The factors impeding maternity service use in this thesis suggest that women with SCIs experience health and health care disparities during pregnancy and childbirth. However, existing maternal health and health care frameworks do not address the characteristics of the health services delivery system, changes in medical technology and social norms relating to treatment of pregnancy and individual determinants (i.e. age, past illness, education) of utilisation [191] for

women with SCIs. This framework underlines the importance of paying attention to various societal and individual determinants that might be helpful in making policy decisions without having only limited information available.

New Technology to Reduce Uncertainty

This doctoral thesis indicates different levels of practitioner-side uncertainty when caring for pregnant women with SCIs. To investigate unclear health symptoms during pregnancy or foetal movements during labour, a non-invasive technique such as thermal imaging could be used [192]. Thermal imaging improves the visibility of objects in dark environments by detecting the objects' infrared radiation and creating images based on this information [193, 194]. It involves no radiation and no contact, is easy to use and is inexpensive. The method has been recently tested in a study with able-bodied women to observe foetal movements in the female abdomen [192]. By thinking of assistive options to support care practitioners, practitioner-side uncertainty can be reduced. A case study could test this.

CONCLUSION

This thesis provides evidence that further improvements in both policy and practice are necessary to provide higher quality health care in maternity services. The outcomes of the studies presented in this thesis provide a deeper understanding of how integrating different views can display the complexity of the actual maternity care situation and be beneficial for discussing how maternity service provision can be optimized by implementing recommendations. The finding that many participants struggle with a lack of information and non-existent or barely accessible service options opens the door not only to clinical research involving different specialties but also to broader research, including health policy and services research. This could reduce the fear and uncertainty felt by pregnant women with SCIs and improve their experiences with pregnancy and childbirth, while also reducing the fears of health practitioners concerning treating pregnant women with SCIs.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This thesis adds to a growing body of empirical research evidence that highlights the unique maternity care needs and actual situation of women with spinal cord injuries (SCIs) and the challenges they encounter in accessing and using health services during pregnancy and birth. In particular, the qualitative and quantitative research approach used to document women's and health providers' experiences helped to understand the challenges women with SCI face in accessing and using maternal health care in Switzerland, as well as provide suggestions for health care services to take the necessary actions to address the situation.

This thesis consists of five chapters. *Chapter 1* provides a general introduction and an overview of the themes of the thesis. The thesis starts with an introduction to maternity and maternity care in Europe and Switzerland. The important aspects relating to health care and maternity care for disabled people are presented. Followed by an overview of the specific challenges of maternity and maternity care in living with a SCI. The overview shows that it is challenging for researchers from different specialty fields to provide consistent answers to some of the important research questions pertaining to pregnancy and birth with an SCI. The most frequently cited causes of this difficulty are the small incidence and the absence of specialised providers as well as the lack of scientific publications, specific sources of information, appropriate standards and available data. *Chapter 1* ends with the rationale of this thesis, including the overall objective and specific aims of the three studies, and ends with the outline of the thesis.

In *Chapters 2 to 4* of the thesis, three sections are presented representing the empirical studies containing concrete analyses from the perspectives of mothers with SCI and the health professionals providing care during the pregnancy and childbirth of women with SCI. None of these empirical investigations extends beyond the national level.

To better comprehend the demands on supply services, the physiologic changes during pregnancy and childbirth in women with SCI must be understood. Typical physiologic changes associated with pregnancy and those unique to SCI can temporarily or permanently affect the health and functioning of women with SCI who become pregnant. To gain a better understanding of these physiologic changes, data was collected from women with SCI who were

concerned about their urologic health and other medical health issues related to problems during pregnancy and childbirth.

Accordingly, the objective of the first study in *Chapter 2* was to identify any medical complications during pregnancy and childbirth for women with SCI in Switzerland and to describe how they dealt with those complications during the perinatal phase. Because of the restricted availability of data in the Swiss Cohort Study (SwiSCI) when the first article was conceived, the approach of using a separate medical questionnaire was decided upon. This approach has its limitations, but it did not preclude employing some sophisticated cohort data approaches and including control groups at a later stage.

Therefore, the article starts by characterising the population of women who became a mother after SCI. Furthermore, the article empirically identifies the main medical complications experienced and explains various ways of dealing with the specific complications related to SCI, such as changing bladder and bowel management. Moreover, in addition to the reasons for prenatal hospitalisation, natal hospitalisation after birth procedures and outcomes were presented separately.

Thus, the collected data gives an overview of the complications and the importance placed on seeking medical advice. The results serve as an indicator of the demand for services. This article demonstrates that pregnancy and delivery in women with SCI is possible without posing intolerable risks to the mother or the child.

The second study presented in *Chapter 3* explores the perceived needs and experiences of mothers with health care services who had given birth to a child after their SCI within the past 15 years. Methods of qualitative content analysis were applied. The approach utilised women's reports of health service experiences to determine service needs and to understand the use of services. Pregnancy after SCI requires extended and tailored health care services. Women's health needs were grouped into six categories in which the need to improve integrated care seemed the most discussed among the women.

Women also described the health professionals they consulted and the facilities they visited for their medical needs. In particular, they required additional medical care or monitoring when the course of the pregnancy was complicated. In some cases, various health institutions were consulted to solve the same health problem, including emergency medicine. Women preferred using local

health services and regular birth hospitals and reported receiving no additional benefits from the services of specialised SCI centres during pregnancy. Finally, the perceived degree of health services utilisation, defined by the length of hospital stays, type of health professionals visited and number of consultations, is presented in the last part of the chapter.

The main contribution of the second article of the thesis is that it is the first work that identifies the service needs of these women in Switzerland and that reconstructs the experiences of health care service utilisation. Moreover, semi-structured interviews informed by a behavioural model of health care utilisation enabled a comprehensive overview of the habits, preferences and reasoning behind health care use. Specifically, this method aims to understand and identify the main health needs and situations confronted by women during their use of services. Thus, needs may be related to different service domains or areas where improvements are needed.

The third study presented in *Chapter 4* describes the challenges of providing adequate care when pregnancy occurs together with another condition such as SCI. During pregnancy, for instance, expertise is required from different medical specialties, especially spinal cord medicine and gynaecology. What appears normal to experts of one specialty could represent a problem for experts from another specialty. Therefore, the aim of this study was to reconstruct the perceptions and experiences of Swiss health care providers in caring for women with SCI during pregnancy and childbirth.

The core category that emerged was 'delivering care under uncertainty during a rare event'. The way health professionals treated their patients was largely influenced by how they conceived their roles and by their feelings of responsibility. My interpretation is that the service providers felt uncertain when treating these women. This uncertainty endangers a service providers ability to treat women with SCI and function optimally, which is closely associated with the ability to control and predict situations. The findings of this study in regards to service providers' experiences describe how efforts to regain certainty were initiated. Causal, contextual and intervening conditions that influence treatment scenarios are also described. The article concludes by highlighting attempts to restore certainty by withstanding or handling uncertainty.

Chapter 5 discusses the findings and provides specific conclusions for the field of Swiss maternity care for women with an SCI. These may be valid for a wider field of disabilities other than SCI.

The thesis concludes by offering suggestions for future research. Rather concrete propositions were made in the three articles of the thesis. In the medical study, the use of more extensive data and sophisticated methodological approaches are proposed, for example, to use cohort data, control groups such as women with SCI without children or able-bodied mothers, and multivariate analyses. In the interview study with mothers, more in-depth research on the factors influencing service needs was suggested. For example, population characteristics and resources that influenced service needs and subsequent use could be explored. The last article suggests that clinical studies realise further investigations to provide a broader base of evidence for decision making and to develop integrated care concepts.

APPENDIX

Appendix 1

Medical questionnaire in German used in study 1	110
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Appendix 2

Demographic questionnaire in German used in study 1 & 2	114
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Appendix 3

Semi-structured questionnaire in German used in study 2	119
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Appendix 4

Semi-structured questionnaire in German used in study 3	124
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MEDIZINISCHER FRAGEBOGEN FÜR MÜTTER MIT EINER QUERSCHNITTLÄHMUNG

VERÄNDERUNGEN WÄHREND DER SCHWANGERSCHAFT

1. Hatten sie Hautprobleme während der Schwangerschaft?
o Ja o Nein
o Dekubitus
o Andere Hautprobleme _____
2. Wurde die Dekubitus-Prophylaxe während der Schwangerschaft verändert?
o Ja o Nein
o Anderes Sitzkissen
o Mehr Ruhephasen/Liegen im Bett
o Andere/weitere Prophylaxe _____
3. Hatten Sie vermehrte Infekte der oberen Luftwege (Lunge, Hals, Nasen, Ohren)?
o Ja o Nein
4. Wurde speziell in der Schwangerschaft eine Thromboseprophylaxe vorgenommen?
o Ja o Nein
o Stützstrümpfe/Antithrombosestrümpfe
o Medikamente: _____
o Beine hochlagern
o Kalte Beinduschen
o Andere Verfahren: _____
5. Veränderung der Anzahl Blaseninfekte während der Schwangerschaft:
+/- _____
6. Wie haben Sie die Blaseninfekte während der Schwangerschaft behandelt?

7. Hatte die Schwangerschaft Einfluss auf die Blasenfunktion (z. B. Inkontinenz, häufiger kathetern) (während/danach)? o Ja o Nein
-
8. Wurde die Behandlung ihrer Blasenfunktion während der Schwangerschaft verändert? (Bsp. Dauerkatheter, andere Medikamente, Botox) o Ja o Nein
-
9. Wer hat Ihnen bei urologischen Problemen Therapiemöglichkeiten vorgeschlagen?
-
10. Haben Sie während/nach der Schwangerschaft Therapien für die Beckenbodenstärkung angewendet? o Ja o Nein / Welche?
-
11. Hatte die Schwangerschaft Einfluss auf die Darmfunktion?
o Ja o Nein/ Welche?
-
12. Änderung der Medikamenteneinnahme während der Schwangerschaft ?
o Ja o Nein
- Verschlechterung Symptome
 - Medikamente während Schwangerschaft nicht erlaubt
 - Andere
13. Haben Sie Alternativmedikation in Anspruch genommen? (z.B. pflanzlich/homöopathisch) o Ja o Nein
14. Mussten Sie während der Schwangerschaft stationär in ein Spital aufgenommen werden? o Ja o Nein
- Dekubitus
 - Autonome Dysreflexie
 - Harnwegsinfekte
 - Infekte der Atemwege
 - Andere:

INFORMATIONEN ÜBER SEXUALITÄT UND SCHWANGERSCHAFT MIT EINER QUERSCHNITTLÄHMUNG

1. Erfahren Sie sexuelle Edukation und Schwangerschaftsberatung während der Erst-Reha? o Ja o Nein

Falls ja, von wem und waren Sie mit der Beratung zufrieden?

2. Wie haben Sie sich sonst über Sexualität und Schwangerschaft mit QS informiert?

- Internet
- Bücher, Zeitschriften
- Peer Counseling
- Bekannte im Rollstuhl
- Medizinisches Personal ausserhalb der Reha-Klinik
- Weitere: _____

GEBURT

- Ist das Kind zur errechneten Zeit geboren worden oder hatten Sie eine Früh- oder Spätgeburt ?

+/- Wochen

- Geburtsart:

- Vaginal

- Kaiserschnitt

- Glocke

- Zange

- Andere: _____

- Erfolgte die Geburt unter Betäubung?

o Ja o Nein

- Periduralanästhesie

- Vollnarkose

- IV. Hatten Sie weitere medizinische Veränderungen, die Sie mit uns gerne teilen möchten?

DEMOGRAPHISCHER FRAGEBOGEN FÜR MÜTTER MIT EINER QUERSCHNITTLÄHMUNG

Im Folgenden möchten wir Ihnen einige Fragen zu Ihrer Person stellen.

GEBURTSDATUM: _____ (TAG / MONAT / JAHR,
Z.B. 18 / 08 / 1942)

WAS IST (SIND) IHRE NATIONALITÄT(EN)?

WAS IST ZURZEIT IHR ZIVILSTAND?

- Ledig (nie verheiratet / getrennt lebend)
- Verheiratet, seit: _____ (Jahr)
- Geschieden, seit: _____ (Jahr)
- Verwitwet, seit: _____ (Jahr)
- Eingetragene Partnerschaft, seit: _____ (Jahr)

HABEN SIE ZURZEIT EINEN FESTEN PARTNER?

- Ja
- Nein

WOHNEN SIE ALLEINE?

- Ja
- Nein

Bitte geben Sie so genau wie möglich das Datum an, an dem Ihre Rückenmarksverletzung eingetreten ist:

_____ (Tag / Monat / Jahr, z.B. 10 / 07 / 1982)

IN WELCHEM JAHR SIND IHR(E) KIND(ER) GEBOREN?

1 Kind

2 Kind

3 Kind

Geburtsdatum: _____

BITTE GEBEN SIE DIE URSACHE IHRER RÜCKENMARKS-
VERLETZUNG AN

Folge eines Unfalls:

→ mehrere Antworten möglich

Unfall bei Sport oder Freizeit

Verkehrsunfall

Sturz

Verletzung durch Gewalteinfluss (z.B. Schussverletzung)

Andere Unfallursache

Folge einer Krankheit:

→ mehrere Antworten möglich

Tumor

Entzündung

Blutung

Infektion

Folge eines medizinischen Eingriffes

Andere Krankheitsursache

Andere Ursache:

HABEN SIE EINE PARA- ODER EINE TETRAPLEGIE?

- Paraplegie, Läsionshöhe: _____
- Tetraplegie, Läsionshöhe: _____

HABEN SIE EINE KOMPLETTE ODER EINE INKOMPLETTE LÄHMUNG?

- Komplet (keine Muskelkraft oder Sensibilität unterhalb der Lähmungshöhe)
- Inkomplett (Muskelkraft oder Sensibilität unterhalb der Lähmungshöhe vorhanden)

WO WAREN SIE ZUR ERSTREHABILITATION?

- Universitätsklinik Balgrist, Zürich
- REHAB Basel
- Clinique Romande de Réadaptation, Sion (suvacare)
- Schweizer Paraplegiker Zentrum (SPZ), Nottwil
- Anderes Rehabilitationszentrum in der Schweiz oder im Ausland:
_____ *(Name/Ort/Land)*
- Anderes Spital, keine spezifische Rehabilitation für die Rückenmarksverletzung
- Weiss nicht

BITTE GEBEN SIE AN, WIE VIELE JAHRE SCHUL- UND BERUFSAUSBILDUNG SIE INSGESAMT ABSOLVIERT HABEN.

→ Bsp.: 6 (Primarschule) + 3 (Sekundarschule) + 4 (Berufslehre) = 13 Jahre.

→ Bsp.: 6 (Primarschule) + 7 (Gymnasium) + 4 (Studium) = 17 Jahre.

Jahre in der Schul- und Berufsausbildung insgesamt: _____ Jahre

Bitte geben Sie Ihren höchsten Bildungsabschluss an:

WAS IST ZURZEIT IHRE BERUFLICHE SITUATION?

→ mehrere Antworten möglich

- Erwerbstätig (Beschäftigung: _____ % Pensum)
- In Ausbildung (Schule, Studium, etc.)
- In einer unbezahlten Arbeit (Umschulung, unbezahltes Praktikum, etc.)
- Arbeitslos (aber auf Arbeitssuche)
- Hausfrau, Hausmann
- Invalidenrente:
 - ¼ / ½ / ¾ / 1
- Im Ruhestand
- Andere, nämlich:

WIE SIND SIE KRANKENVERSICHERT?

- Allgemein
- Halbprivat
- Privat
- Anderes Modell
- Weiss nicht

WIE HOCH UMGEFÄHR IST DAS GESAMTE MONATLICHE NETTOEINKOMMEN IN IHREM HAUSHALT?

Das Nettoeinkommen ist die Summe aus allen Einkommen von allen Haushaltsmitgliedern (inkl. IV-Rente), nach Abzug der obligatorischen Sozialversicherungs- und Pensionskassenbeiträge. Das Nettoeinkommen ist also das, was Sie monatlich tatsächlich ausbezahlt bekommen.

*Falls Sie Alimente erhalten: Zählen Sie diese bitte zum Nettoeinkommen.
Falls Sie Alimente zahlen: Ziehen Sie diese bitte vom Nettoeinkommen ab.*

- Weniger als 1500 Franken
- Zwischen 1500 und 3000 Franken
- Zwischen 3000 und 4500 Franken
- Zwischen 4500 und 6000 Franken
- Zwischen 6000 und 7500 Franken
- Zwischen 7500 und 9000 Franken
- Mehr als 9000 Franken

Herzlichen Dank für das Ausfüllen des Fragebogens. Ihr Mitmachen freut uns sehr!

Nehmen Sie bitte den Fragebogen und die unterschriebene Einverständniserklärung am Studientag mit. Damit erklären Sie sich mit der Teilnahme an der Studie einverstanden.

SEMI-STRUKTURIERTER INTERVIEW LEITFADEN FÜR FOKUSGRUPPEN-INTERVIEWS

Allgemeine Begrüssung und Informationen zur Durchführung	
Begrüssung:	<i>„Wir möchten uns ganz herzlich bei Ihnen für Ihr Kommen und Ihre Teilnahme an dieser Studie bedanken. Sie wurden zu dieser Studie angefragt, weil uns Ihre Meinung zu dem Thema „wie sehen optimale Versorgungsdienstleistungen bzw. -angebote für querschnittgelähmte Frauen während der Schwangerschaft und Geburt aus“ interessiert. Die Erfahrungen zu diesem Thema können sehr unterschiedlich sein, deswegen ist uns die Meinung von jedem einzelnen von Ihnen sehr wichtig. Wir wissen, dass Ihre Teilnahme für Sie mit einem gewissen Aufwand verbunden ist, umso mehr möchten wir uns dafür bei Ihnen bedanken. Diese Studie ist kein Test oder eine Untersuchung, sondern sie soll einen Einblick zu dem Thema geben, der für zukünftige Entwicklungen von Bedeutung sein kann.“</i>
Ziel der Studie:	<i>Die Studie untersucht, wie Frauen mit einer Querschnittlähmung in der Schweiz während der Schwangerschaft und Geburt versorgt worden sind. Das Ziel der Studie ist, die persönlichen Erfahrungen mit den verschiedenen Fachpersonen und Dienstleistungsstellen zu erfassen, was gut daran war und was sie sich anders gewünscht hätten, damit an die verschiedenen Organisationen (Spitäler, Praxen, Kursveranstalter) und Fachpersonen Empfehlungen abgegeben werden können.</i>
Vertraulichkeit der Informationen:	<i>„Um alle Aussagen auswerten zu können, werden wir dieses Interview mit einem Aufnahmegerät aufzeichnen, um es später abschreiben zu können. Ihre Angaben werden dabei vollständig anonymisiert, so dass sie keiner Person mehr namentlich zugeordnet werden können. Ausserdem werden Ihre Teilnahme und auch alle Äusserungen, die in diesem Interview fallen, vertraulich behandelt. Nur unser Forscher-Team hat Zugang zu diesen Informationen.“</i>

<p>Regeln des Interviews:</p>	<p><i>„Für die Durchführung des Gruppen-Interviews gibt es ein paar Regeln, die ich jetzt erläutern möchte:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Versuchen Sie immer von sich selbst und nicht von anderen zu sprechen.</i> - <i>Lassen Sie die Äusserungen der anderen gelten. Wir wollen möglichst viele Eindrücke sammeln und diese können natürlich sehr unterschiedlich sein.</i> - <i>Respektieren Sie die Äusserungen der anderen: Was in diesem Raum gesagt wird, bleibt in diesem Raum.</i> - <i>Lassen Sie die anderen aussprechen und genügend Zeit, ihre Eindrücke zu schildern.</i> - <i>Es gibt keine falschen oder richtigen Antworten.</i> - <i>Haben Sie Fragen oder Kommentare hierzu?“</i>
<p>Interview-Leitfaden</p>	
<p>Eröffnung:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>„Ich möchte Sie bitten, sich selbst kurz vorzustellen und wenn Sie wollen, kurz zu erzählen, wie Sie leben, wie viele Kinder sie haben und falls Sie Arbeiten, was Sie beruflich machen...“</i>
<p>Einführung zum Thema:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>„Ich möchte gerne mehr über Ihre Zeit während der Schwangerschaft erfahren. Wie war das für sie, als sie erfahren haben, dass sie schwanger sind? Hat sich etwas für sie geändert?</i> <p>[Medikamente absetzen, vermehrte Spastik, Hilfsmittel zusätzliche/ändern, wegen morgendlicher Übelkeit]</p>
<p>Übergang:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>„Sie haben in Ihren Berichten an verschiedenen Stellen aufgezeigt, von wem Sie professionelle Unterstützung erhalten haben, z.B. [Hebammen,</i>

	<p>Gynäkologen, Urologen, Paraplegiologen....] <i>Gab es weitere Fachpersonen oder auch Institutionen, die Ihnen in dieser Zeit geholfen haben?</i></p> <p>[evtl. auch Peers, Alternativmediziner, Drogisten, Masseur, Geburtsvorbereitungskurse?]</p>
<p>Schlüsselfragen</p>	
<p>Status quo und Bedarfsaufnahme:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>„Welche Unterstützung haben Sie vom Gesundheitssystem (d. h. Fachpersonen oder Institutionen) erhalten und welche Unterstützung haben sie nicht erhalten?“</i> <p>[Haben Sie einen passenden Gynäkologen gefunden? Spezieller therapeutischer Bedarf, Informationen, Wissen, etc.]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Inwieweit waren welche Leistungen für sie nötig? Haben sie diese erhalten oder nicht erhalten, obwohl sie sie gebraucht hätten? Haben sie evtl. gar zu viele Leistungen erhalten?</i> <p>[Hätten Zusatzuntersuchungen nur wegen der Paraplegie vermieden werden können? Untersuchungen wegen mangelnder Deckung nicht bezahlt? Hätten Sie sich mehr oder umfangreicheres Wissen der Fachpersonen über Paraplegie oder Urologie gewünscht?]</p>
<p>Einflussfaktoren für Versorgung:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Wir haben bereits verschiedenes über ihren damaligen Bedarf oder über Wünsche usw gehört..... was waren besonders hinderliche oder förderliche „Sachen“/Faktoren für den Erhalt von Leistungen, Wissen, Informationen?</i> <p>[Bauliche Barrieren, Versicherungsdeckung, wusste</p>

	einfach nicht wo zu fragen, Internet-Wissen]
Zufriedenheit mit Versorgung:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>“Wie zufrieden waren sie mit den Leistungen des Fachpersonals, welches sie während der Schwangerschaft und Geburt begleitet hat?“</i> <p>[Was/wer würden sie weiterempfehlen und was/wer überhaupt nicht?]</p>
Medizinischer Bedarf, Urologie:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>„Sie haben im Gruppengespräch mehrmals dieses Problem xxx (medizinisches Problem, Inkontinenz und Harnwegsinfekte) erwähnt. Ich möchte dieses Thema vertiefen. Mit wem haben Sie welche urologischen Probleme besprochen und haben Sie eine für Sie zufriedenstellende Lösung gefunden? Falls ja, wie und falls nein, warum nicht?“</i> <p>[Wie haben sie die Blaseninfekte behandelt? Mit Antibiotika oder anderen Mitteln? Haben sie da jemanden um Rat gefragt?]</p>
Verbesserungsvorschläge:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Wie sollte die Versorgung in Zukunft für werdende Mütter mit QS aussehen? Was sollte besser sein? Was sollten die bis jetzt genannten Fachpersonen aus ihren persönlichen Erfahrungen lernen?</i> • <i>Damit wir in einer nützlichen Frist bereits erste Änderungen bzw. Verbesserungen einführen könnten, welche wären die angesagtesten? Haben Sie Vorschläge/Ideen dazu?</i> <p>[Evtl. Internetplattform, Kompetenzzentrum mit qualifiziertem Personal (von Frauenarzt-Hebammen-Pflegepersonal-Peer) oder reicht eine Telefonhotline aus?]</p>

Appendix 3 : Semi-structured questionnaire in German used in study 2

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>„Würden Sie ihre Umgebung verlassen und die Hilfe eines Kompetenzzentrums während der Schwangerschaft und der Geburt annehmen?“</i>
<p>Abschlussbemerkungen</p>	
<p>Danke und Verabschiedung:</p>	<p><i>„Wir möchten uns bei Ihnen ganz herzlich für die Teilnahme am Gespräch danken und zum Abschluss noch einmal nachfragen, ob wir Ihrer Meinung nach in unserem Gespräch alle wichtigen Aspekte angesprochen haben. Fällt jemandem noch etwas Wichtiges ein, was bisher zu kurz gekommen ist? Oder hat jemand von Ihnen das Gefühl, bisher nicht richtig zu Wort gekommen zu sein und möchte noch Einschätzungen aus seiner Perspektive ergänzen?“</i></p> <p><i>„Wir bedanken uns nochmals für Ihre Zeit und Ihren Beitrag und wünschen Ihnen eine gute Heimreise“</i></p>

SEMI-STRUKTURIERTES LEITFADENINTERVIEW: EXPERTEN - STUDIE

Persönliches oder evtl. telefonisches Interview

Telefontermin

Guten Tag ...,

Wir fñhrend zum Thema Schwangerschaft und Geburt mit einer Querschnittlähmung eine Studie durch. Haben Sie eine Frau mit einer Rückenmarksverletzung während der Schwangerschaft oder Geburt begleitet?

Dürfte ich Ihnen zu einem späteren Zeitpunkt telefonisch oder persönlich einige Fragen dazu stellen? Ca. 30 Min, wann dürfte ich Ihnen nochmals anrufen?..

Sie werden in den nächsten Tagen per Post Angaben über die Studie erhalten und ich werde Ihnen auch nochmals den Interview-Termin bestätigen.

Interview

Herzlichen Dank, dass Sie an unserer Studie teilnehmen. Ich fasse nochmals kurz zusammen, worum es in unserer Studie geht.

Einleitung

Das Ziel der Studie ist, die Versorgungssituation von Frauen mit einer Querschnittlähmung in der Schweiz zu untersuchen. Dazu führen wir diverse Studien durch, u. a. eine Interviewstudie mit den Experten.

Die Experten werden zu den medizinischen Betreuungs-Bedürfnissen der Frauen während der SS und Geburt befragt; welche beeinflussende Faktoren für eine Inanspruchnahme von Leistungen eine Rolle gespielt haben; welche Dienstleistungen genutzt wurden und wie die Frauen ihrer Ansicht nach mit den erhaltenen Dienstleistungen zufrieden waren. Ebenfalls werden Verbesserungsvorschläge erfragt.

*In diesem Zusammenhang möchten wir Ihnen nun einige Fragen stellen.
Möchten Sie sich kurz vorstellen? (Spital, Praxis, Fachgebiet, etc.)*

Bedarf

Aus welchem Anlass bzw. mit welchem Behandlungsbedarf kamen die schwangeren Frauen mit einer QS zu ihnen?

Was denken Sie, was sind generell die Probleme von Frauen mit einer QS oder Frauen im Rollstuhl während der SS und Geburt? (Kontextfrage!, Versorgungsbedarf)

Inanspruchnahme (Type, Setting)

Und welche (Gesundheits-) Dienstleistungen haben Sie bei Frauen mit einer QS erbracht?

Welche Erfahrung haben Sie mit der Betreuung/Pflege querschnittgelähmter Frauen gemacht? War die Betreuung/Pflege für Sie anders als die von nichtgelähmten Frauen? Wenn ja: In wie fern anders? Wenn nein: Wie erklären Sie sich das? (z.B. Immobilität, Hilfsmittel, Pflege-/Betreuungsaufwand, assoziierte med. Probleme/Fragestellungen)?

Ich nehme an, dass die Behandlungen in ihrer Praxis/Spital stattfanden.

Beeinflussende Faktoren

Wie würden Sie den Zugang zu ihrer Praxis/Spital für eine Frau im Rollstuhl als beschreiben?

- *In wie fern ist Ihre Einrichtung barrierefrei? Wo sehen Sie noch Barrieren und Mobilitätseinschränkungen für querschnittgelähmte Frauen?*
- *Eingang, Parkplätze, WC, Untersuchungsliegen, Umkleide Toiletten? Nachfrage, was genau vorliegt und falls Barrieren vorhanden sind: Denken Sie man könnte etwas daran ändern?*

Gab es evtl. andere Faktoren, ausser dem medizinischen Bedarf im engeren Sinne, die eine Inanspruchnahme von Dienstleistungen beeinflusst haben?

(War beispielsweise das Wissen der Frau über möglich auftretende Komplikationen in ihrem speziellen Fall von Vorteil, spielte die Versicherungsdeckung eine Rolle oder war immer alles klar und einfach?)

Bsp. von Anschlussfragen:

- *War die Patientin bereits vor ihrer Schwangerschaft bei Ihnen in Behandlung/Pflege?*
- *Haben Sie zusätzliche Fachmeinungen eingeholt? Falls ja, wo? Waren die Informationen zufriedenstellend? Wie informierten Sie sich sonst noch über mögliche Risiken bei Schwangerschaft und Geburt einer Frau mit QS?*
- *Haben Sie schwangere Patientinnen an Kollegen überwiesen? Wenn ja, warum?*
- *Haben Sie mit einem Spital zusammengeschafft? Wenn ja, wie war die Zusammenarbeit mit dem Spital-Team (Hebamme & Pflegende)?*
- *Könnten Sie aufgrund Ihrer Erfahrungen eine Institution benennen, an die sich betreuende Fachpersonen (Mediziner, Hebammen oder Pflegende) mit Fragen bei querschnittgelähmten Frauen während der SS wenden sollten?*

Verbesserungsvorschläge

- *Wie könnte die Versorgung für querschnittgelähmte Frauen verbessert werden?*

Abschlussfrage

- Gibt es weitere Erlebnisse, Ereignisse oder Eindrücke, die Sie uns zum Thema Versorgung von querschnittgelähmten Frauen während der Schwangerschaft und Geburt gern schildern möchten oder habe ich vergessen etwas zu fragen?
- Würden Sie wiederum eine Frau mit Querschnittlähmung während der SS begleiten?

Falls noch Zeit übrig ist:

Richtlinien Ihrer Fachgesellschaft/Forschung

- Ist Ihnen bekannt, ob in Ihrer Fachgesellschaft Guidelines, Richtlinien oder Experten-Gruppen existieren, an die Sie sich bei Bedarf wenden können?
- Ist das Thema Schwangerschaft und Querschnittlähmung in Ihrer Fachgruppe ein relevantes Diskussionsthema (z. B. Präsentationen auf Fachtagungen, Workshops zum Thema, Kompetenz-Zentren)?
- Sehen Sie eine Notwendigkeit, Forschung auf diesem Sektor zu intensivieren?

